

UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
FILOZOFSKA FAKULTETA
ODDELEK ZA FILOZOFIJO
ODDELEK ZA ANGLISTIKO IN AMERIKANISTIKO

STELLA ASLANI

**A Work of Art as an Expression of Society
and Concrete Examples From Yann Martel's
*Life of Pi***

**Umetniško delo kot izraz družbe
in konkretni primeri iz romana Yanna Martela
*Pijevo življenje***

Magistrsko delo

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Abstract

A Work of Art as an Expression of Society and Concrete Examples from Yann Martel's *Life of Pi*

What do art, literature and society have in common? Do they just happen to exist alongside each other, or are they somehow connected? This thesis deals with the relation between society and art, more specifically, literature; how a work of art is an expression of society and how that can be seen not only through a long interlacing history of literature's and society's change, but also in a modern novel, *Life of Pi*, written by Yann Martel.

The thesis starts off by establishing the relation between literature and society, namely, by revisiting the history of literature and literary theory. Later it moves on to establishing a background for analysis and interpretation of *Life of Pi* by revisiting the history of fables, and introducing and analysing two literary examples, *Animal Farm* by George Orwell and *Tainaron* by Leena Krohn. Before detailed analysis of *Life of Pi* is offered, a short introduction to the origins of the novel is made. This will prove to be crucial for interpretation of *Life of Pi* alongside with a later established philosophical background that stands in a direct relation with the fable background and the results of the analysis of *Life of Pi*.

What can be concluded is not only that literature and society are connected and that a work of art definitely is an expression of society – which is obvious from merely revisiting the history of literature – but that art plays a vital role in changing and reshaping society. By analysing *Life of Pi* according to vast and different pre-established backgrounds the relation between art and society becomes even more obvious as well as the hints of what is wrong with our society and what has to be done to make a change. *Life of Pi* teaches that old long-lasting beliefs are not necessarily good for our society and that change is inevitable for preventing society from stagnation. It also shows that a work of art is not only an expression of society pointing out what is wrong with it, but it also points out which direction to take in order for society to change for the better. Art is a powerful tool often taken too lightly by society.

Key words: art, literature, society, change, Martel, Orwell, Krohn

Izveček

Umetniško delo kot izraz družbe in konkretni primeri iz romana Yanna Martela *Pijevo življenje*

Kaj imajo umetnost, književnost in družba skupnega? Morda zgolj slučajno obstajajo ena zraven druge? Magistrsko delo se ukvarja z odnosom med družbo in umetnostjo, natančneje književnostjo; s tem, kako je umetniško delo odraz družbe, in s tem, da je to razvidno ne samo skozi dolgo in zapleteno zgodovino sprememb v književnosti in družbi, ampak tudi v sodobnem romanu *Pijevo življenje* avtorja Yanna Martela.

Magistrsko delo se prične z vzpostavljanjem odnosa med književnostjo in družbo, in sicer z uvodom v zgodovino književnosti in literarne teorije. Kasneje ustvari ozadje za analizo in interpretacijo *Pijevega življenja* tako, da nas popelje skozi zgodovino basni, uvede in analizira dva literarna primera, Orwellovo *Živalsko farmo* in *Tainaron* avtorice Leene Krohn. Pred podrobno analizo *Pijevega življenja* sledi še kratek uvod o izvoru romana. Ta kratek uvod je pomemben za interpretacijo *Pijevega življenja* skupaj s kasneje odkritim filozofskim ozadjem, ki stoji v neposrednem razmerju z ozadjem basni in rezultati analize *Pijevega življenja*.

Moč je skleniti, da sta književnost in družba ne samo povezana in da umetniško delo ni zgolj izraz družbe – kar je razvidno že iz zgodovine književnosti –, temveč tudi, da umetnost igra ključno vlogo v spreminjanju in preoblikovanju družbe. Ob analizi *Pijevega življenja* glede na obsežna in zelo drugačna prej vzpostavljena ozadja, odnos med umetnostjo in družbo postane toliko bolj očiten, enako kot namigi glede tega, kaj je narobe z družbo in kaj je treba narediti, da bi prišlo do spremembe. *Pijevo življenje* bralca uči, da globoko zakoreninjena prepričanja niso nujno dobra za družbo ter da je za preprečitev stagnacije družbe sprememba neizogibna. Ravno tako pokaže, da umetniško delo ni zgolj odraz družbe, ki opozarja na to, kaj je narobe z njo, ampak nam tudi kaže smernice, kako bi se družba lahko spremenila na boljše. Umetnost je močno orodje, katerega družba ne dojema kot takega.

Ključne besede: umetnost, književnost, družba, sprememba, Martel, Orwell, Krohn

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	1
Literature and society	5
1.1. The history of literature.....	5
1.2. Literary theory	10
Formalism	13
Structuralism	14
Post-structuralism	15
Reader response theory.....	16
Animals and stories	19
2.1. Fables	19
2.2. <i>Animal Farm</i>	21
2.3. <i>Tainaron: Mail From Another City</i>	23
2.4. What do fable, <i>Animal Farm</i> and <i>Tainaron</i> have in common?.....	24
<i>Life of Pi</i>	27
3.1. Canadian literature and animals.....	27
3.2. <i>Life of Pi</i> – analysis part 1	30
Structure	31
Language, style and tone.....	34
Plot.....	38
Symbolism	45
Themes	48
3.3. <i>Life of Pi</i> – analysis part 2	54
Philosophical background	54
Interpretation.....	60
Conclusion.....	66
Povzetek.....	71
References	75

Introduction

Art. What is art? Linguistically speaking it is a word, more precisely a noun, consisting of three distinguished sounds. Yet this simple word has stirred up the human world for ages, becoming an everlasting question many have tried to find an answer to but failed. By failed I do not mean that no theory of art is true, just that art changes and so does the answer to what art is.

However, although the world, society and art change, one thing remains certain. Art and society are two ever-intertwining spheres. Art is important, if not the most important part of human life. One may ask what makes art and human life irreversibly connected. How can a simple art be so powerful? What makes it special, and most of all, what it is here for? The answers to all these questions are simple but, at the same time, the most difficult ever.

Simply stating that art and society go hand in hand is a powerful thesis on its own, but in order to fully grasp its power and size, we must first understand and admit to ourselves certain facts about art. First, art is a crucial part of society. Its influence runs deep to society's very core. Society would not be what it is if it were not for art.

Human history knows many different types of societies – from ancient societies we still strive to learn more about, to an amazing range of societies actively existing this very moment I write. All these societies differ in one way or another but the one thing they all have in common is art. Every society we know about has its own version of what they consider art to be. Egyptians had Egyptian art, Europeans have their history of European art, and African tribes have their wide range of tribal art. Therefore, art comes in many shapes; if not more, than at least as many as types of societies existed on our planet called Earth. Moreover, a specific kind of art, for example European art, has its genres and each genre has its subgenres, but art does not stop at that. It goes ever further and deeper like the tree of life. There seems to be no end. Only when we grasp this amazingly wide span of art can we move forward to yet another magical property of art.

Societies consist of humans. Humans are the centre figure of everything. Everything is either made by humans, imagined by humans or destroyed by humans. Therefore, it is not strange that art also sees humans as its big centrepiece. It is a human product, more precisely, a product of human imagination. Besides, it is so much

more. It is not just a simple product to be used on a daily basis; it is not a human creation for the benefit of society as whole; it is rather a creation of human society for the benefit of individuals lost in this humongous being called society. Humans create art and they still find it to be the most intriguing thing there is, as if it were not made by them in the first place.

Art has some sort of transcendental value, something magical and untouchable. It is no wonder that, although a human product, art will forever remain mystery. Why is this so, you may ask? The answer is simple. Through art, no matter what kind of art, one expresses one's true self, one's true identity, one's true life. Moreover, through art we can see the true face of our society; its problems, wishes and cravings. We can form an opinion and show it to everyone who wishes to see. Art touches us on some deep level. There is no escaping from it.

Art mirrors society, its events and problems. Aesthetic questions are never purely aesthetic but concern different fields of human life. By answering and solving aesthetic questions and problems we can also find answers and solutions to the problems concerning our society.

Moreover, if we take a closer look at the history of art we can see how it developed alongside great and sometimes even revolutionary changes in society. Sometimes it reflected society's progress yet, more often than not, it has dictated the progress. By studying art, its progress and its changes we can study society itself. We can study a society's political, personal and social growth or downfall. Art is one beautiful diary that says it all. One must simply have the courage to crack it open, peak inside and investigate. Art reflects society's soul and reveals its remedy.

As already mentioned, there are many different kinds of art, and as many genres and subgenres. To make the life bearable over next 60 pages or so, the search through the vastness of art needs to be narrowed. First, mostly European and American art will be looked at, since it is the art I grew up with and which lighted my way through life to this very moment. Then again, the thesis is a joined thesis between two majors, Philosophy and English, so it is only natural to further narrow the search to literature only. All examples, approaches and analyses are strictly literature based. Otherwise, there might be a confusion regarding the form of expression or combining and linking examples to each other.

Examples are, however, not strictly art written in English, since narrowing down the search to European and American art is narrow enough. A certain broadness needs

to be present in order to support the claim in best possible way. Therefore, certain references to Finnish art are present, the book *Tainaron*, as well as folk art and even religious art, while at the same time the main example, *Life of Pi*, remains art written in English language.

Since literature is the main theme of the thesis, placing it into right historical surrounding is necessary. Therefore, aesthetic analysis and historical references needed for establishment of a firm basis and sound walls are strictly literature related – that is, they pertain to literary theory and criticism, and its history. Even the analysis is strictly literary analysis of the text, albeit divided into two seemingly separate types of it.

The general relation between art and society is being replaced by the relation between literature and society and the influence they have on each other throughout history. After the relationship between society and its twin in literature is established, by closely studying the history of literature and literary theory, the objective becomes to establish the relationship between *Life of Pi* and, not only society, but also the general scope of the thesis. This is easily done by introducing other literature examples, which, although seemingly different by form, language and genre, have a strong connection to each other hidden both in their form and story. These books will not be analyzed in depth, rather serve as a smooth introduction to the analysis of *Life of Pi*, by showing us the main literary, institutionally accepted, tools used in their analysis that are later used for *Life of Pi*'s analysis as well.

Detailed analysis of *Life of Pi* follows. The above mentioned literary tools are used to establish book's role and place in literature. Establishing its role, place, form, and genre is not nearly enough. By using only specific literary tools neither aesthetic evaluation of the work of art nor full interpretation of the book is possible. This leads us to, as I call it, non-formal analysis of the book, i.e. the interpretation of the book which not all literary critiques would approve of. To establish the grounds for such an interpretation, philosophical background is laid out first. This background is crucial for the final and complete analysis of *Life of Pi*. *Life of Pi* as an allegory of society itself.

The thesis is theoretical and research based. A wide range of literature concerning art and its relation to society will lay grounds for detailed analysis of one specific book, *Life of Pi*, through which the problem of art and society is further developed. Descriptive and explanatory analysis will dominate, with descriptive analysis laying basics for explanatory analysis.

The objectives of the thesis are as follows: to establish a relationship between society and art, more specific, literature; to study and show the progress of literature and its counterpart literary theory throughout their and human history; to establish literary tools used for analysis by introducing two literary examples; to analyse *Life of Pi*; to further lay philosophical grounds for interpretation; to interpret *Life of Pi* according to previously established philosophical ground; to establish that both traditional analysis and interpretational analysis of the book are necessary to full understand a work of art and its relation to the real life and society.

By following these objectives the question what art teaches us, shows us and tells us is answered. The question which literary theory to follow and use is also answered, as well as the question what is society's next step.

Literature and society

1.1. The history of literature

Written words date far back, to the third millennium BC. The initial uses of writing were strictly practical, yet without them today's literature would not exist. Although the initial uses of writing tend to be an equivalent of today's to-do lists, contracts and drafts of different accounts, from a historical point of view they still have a story to tell. They tell the story of their time. Without Egyptian hieroglyphs, Sumerian writings or logos from ancient Chinese regimes their story, the story about how they lived, what they believed in and how their everyday life looked like would be incomplete. True, all these writings are far from what we consider literature – written works that have artistic, creative and lasting value – to be today but their final purpose, so many years after they were written, is not drastically different from the purpose literature has today. They all tell some story, one way or another.

Some may find my claim needless because not all writing, according to the above definition of writing, constitutes literature. So why do I talk about simple, practical written data telling a story? Am I saying that we should all forget what we know about literature and what literature is and re-evaluate it? Am I saying that everything written is literature? I am not. I have no intention at all to speculate or re-investigate what falls under literature and what not. There are numerous reasons why I have no intention of doing so, but two stand out.

First, the question what is literature is not so different than the question what is art. I already tackled that question in my bachelor's thesis by investigating both aesthetic value of the work of art and the role of art critics. If I extend my conclusion of what art is to what literature is, the conclusion would be similar to John M. Ellis' argument about the term 'literature':

Weeds are not particular kinds of plant, but just any kind of plant which for some reason or another a gardener does not want around. Perhaps 'literature' means something like the opposite: any kind of writing which for some reason or another somebody values highly. (Eagleton 1996, 8)

The definition of art, as well as the definition of literature, differs not only from one critic to another, from one literary theory to another, but also from one period of

history to another. Society changes and so does literature and its definition. It might happen that the definition of literature is addressed on several occasions in the scope of this thesis, but never with the intention of defining it, but rather connecting its progress and change to a broader theme.

Second, the objective is to show and establish the relationship between literature and society. To do so, it is important to show the progress written word and society underwent almost hand in hand. The first written words were far from being considered as literature, at least not in today's sense; they were a human product, a product of society's development. Their purpose was recording the state of society and its process. Today their purpose shifted from recording to telling a story and by doing so they teach us about our past. If this kind of shift in purpose is present in the very first writings, what purpose did later writings, the ones considered literature, have, and what purpose do they still have today?

The *Epic of Gilgamesh*, an epic poem from ancient Mesopotamia about the quests and heroic actions of Gilgamesh, king of Uruk, is considered to be one of the first instances of literature. Note that it is not the only epic poem that found its place among the pioneers of literature. There is also the *Mahabharata*, 'Great Epic of the Bharata Dynasty', and, to most far more familiar, the *Iliad* and *Odyssey*, believed to be composed in the eight century BC. What these four epics have in common, although they are from different periods and come from different cultures, is that they all tell a story. The story they tell is the story about heroes, semi-gods and kings. The *Iliad* tells the heroic story of the Trojan War, while the *Odyssey* tells the adventure story of Odysseus's quest.

Both the *Iliad* and *Odyssey* are considered to be based upon historical events, as well as the *Mahabharata*. The only difference is that the *Mahabharata* is based on the events of Indian culture, while the *Iliad* and *Odyssey* are based on the events of Greek culture. Nonetheless, the purpose of the four epics is the same. They record historical events in a heroic form. Once again the written word emerges from society itself.

Aside from epic poems there was one other popular form of writing present at that time. The form that was even more highly valued than the epics – religious books. In India one can find *Vedas* and *Upanishads*, in China *Daodejing*, in Egypt the *Book of the Dead*, and in western culture the *Bible*. It seems that the only thing these books have in common is the fact that they all stand as a testament of their religion, but that

is not the case. It is true, all of these books are religious books and, naturally, their main theme is religion; however, the things they also have in common include their practicality and use, their meaning in the time they were written and their meaning from today's point of view.

So let us start with books' practicality. The *Rigveda*, the oldest of all *Vedas*, is the collection of temple hymns, while all other *Vedas* are collections of priestly chants and prayers. The *Daodejing* is a manual for alternative religion in China used by those who follow Daoism instead of Confucianism. The Egyptian *Book of the Dead* served as a funerary text, as a collection of a varying selection of religious and magical texts. In short, they are all practical books. Their use was essentially religious but their practicality and use never diminished their broader meaning for the people of their time. Without these manuals and collections people would have been lost and their belief scattered. The books did not have only practical value of what to say and when to say it during ceremony, but deeper, almost intrinsic value. Similarly as epics did, these books also held society's morale and obedience high.

Their practical value in today's rather secularized atmosphere is close to none, with the notable exception of those who continue to practice these religions. And even then not all parts of the books are practical any more. Now they are beautiful examples of early literature. What kind of language was used, what kind of structure, what themes were covered and why is analysed. As their practical value changed and they became more valuable as historical documents, so did their meaning. They are no longer strictly practical religious books with the intrinsic value but religious books of one historical era. They tell the story of that society and its people. How people back then lived, how they loved, what they believed in, what were their biggest fears and wishes and how they died. The very core of the society in question can be read from the pages of seemingly simple religious manual.

To explore the relationship between society and literature beyond the first writings and religious books, a look at literature examples from pioneering times of western culture has to be taken. The pioneer of western culture is Greek culture. Western culture owes it so much that it seems only natural to investigate and reconsider Greek literature and its relationship to society then and today. Greek literature consisted of a great Greek tragedy and comedy, which, although, less valued had the same, if not a bigger, impact on Greek society. Greek tragedy is considered to be based upon the stories of Greek myth. Its structure was strict, as well as the use of

meter, for example, spoken iambic trimeter. In it one can see the seeds of drama as it existed today and because Greek tragedy had a great impact on Ancient Rome and Renaissance.

However, putting the strict structure and influences aside, the story Greek tragedy tells and what it represents asks for further attention. As mentioned, the story of each tragedy was based upon the stories of Greek myth. For example, Sophocles' *Antigone* was inspired by princess Antigone from Greek mythology. All the characters were well known to the public, since they were mythical characters held in a high esteem. One could ask why the need to write about and stage theatre plays about characters that are not real and date centuries back. The answer is that by using Greek mythical past as a metaphor tragedians showed and tackled contemporary problems – problems from the democratic, political and cultural life. This is something playwrights have done ever since the end of Greek culture to today. They use literature as a tool for making a statement about the society they live in.

Greek tragedy had one more side, the side I argue literature in general has. By making the problems of society obvious through means of metaphor, they also offered a solution to the problem. It was never a direct solution, rather an insinuation of what is valued by society and what every individual should strive for. For example, *Antigone* teaches us that we should respect laws that act in accordance with human morality and which foster human dignity.

On the other hand, Greek comedy was never as valued as highly as Greek tragedy was since it never ended with catharsis. It was considered to have one purpose only – the purpose of entertaining people. This is where most got it wrong. Greek comedy has, I dare to say, even bigger catharsis value to the society. By satirizing contemporary faults of people it teaches us about society and shows us the negative side of society. The level of clearness about what is wrong and what should be valued is different in comedy than in tragedy. Tragedy gives us all the necessary information on its open palm, while comedy criticizes society and by doing so points out what is wrong with it. Furthermore, by pointing out what is wrong with society it also points out what is valued and should be strived for. This is achieved by wrapping the issues in a nice glowing wrapping paper otherwise known as humour.

It could be said that to decode tragedy is easy when the right tools are at disposal, while decoding comedy asks for a slightly more trained use of tools. Both tragedy and

comedy serve the same purpose. The purpose of telling the story which tells the story of the society work comes from.

The above small analysis of Greek drama was not only about Greek drama itself. It can be extended to the drama and literature ever since. Having that in mind, the analysis of the history of literature from one era to another stops with Greek drama. Later periods of literature tend to expand more and more and are far more complex. Each period borrows something from the previous period and adds its own things, such as the new approach or new genre. This is the case even with Greek drama. Euripides introduced the new, unconventional view by approaching Greek myth from new angles or viewing mythological characters in terms of their human frailties (History World 2015).

The division of literature into several different eras makes the examination of literature easier. It also shows that literature is the product of society and it goes hand in hand with its change and progress. The main literature periods generally have the same name as the main periods of human history. Each era brings something new to society. Something new happens that reshapes society, that it reshapes its old foundations. The same happens with literature. Each change, be it progress or decay, in society reshapes literature. It reshapes it in such way that some themes no longer occur while new arrive; some techniques become questioned while others become valuable; some writing may even become forbidden and they survive by falling underground. In short, by changing and evolving, society redefines literature again and again.

1.2. Literary theory

Since the main theme of this thesis is literature, it is only natural to mention literary theory. Everything that exists in this world had, has, or will have a theory written about it. Therefore, it is not strange that, eventually, literary theory emerged.

What literary theory is and when did it come to live are natural questions to ask. The answer to the first question is already given in the name itself. It is a theory about literature.

However, the short answer does not say much. It opens more questions than it provides answers to. One question that pops to mind is the question I have already specified I will not try to answer. It is the question that seeks the answer to what literature is. If literary theory is a theory about literature, then what is literature? According to literary theory literature is many things. Each literary theory school has its own definition of literature. In short, the answer to what literature is changes endlessly. It would be safer to say that literary theory is a theory that strives to define literature, and does that by defining the methods for analysing literature, the methods for practical reading of literature. As Vince Brewton said:

Literary theory is a description of the underlying principles, one might say the tools, by which we attempt to understand literature. (Brewton 2015),

or as Terry Eagleton compared literary theory to Tradition:

A literary work can be valid only by existing in the Tradition, as a Christian can be saved only by living in God; all poetry may be literature but only some poetry is Literature, depending on whether or not the Tradition happens to flow through it. (Eagleton 1996, 34)

To give the list of the exact methods used by different literary theory schools and their answers to what literature is would be close to impossible. There are many literary schools that define their own methods, their own approach and their own theory. Each literary school redefines literature as each historical era does. The only difference is that it redefines it in what is considered to be strictly professionally manner. It takes into question the history of literature, previous theories and their methods, the previous canon and its interpretations, creating its own look at it.

The questions such as why there are so many different literary schools and theories and why there cannot be only one or none follow. The answer to why there should be any literary theory at all is, as Terry Eagleton has said, “that with some kind of theory, however unreflective and implicit, we would not know what a ‘literary work’ was in the first place, or how we were to read it” (Eagleton 1996, x). If nothing else, literary theory helps us to learn to read and appreciate literature.

The answer to the question why there are so many literary theory schools is a harder one. There cannot be only one definition of literature since literature changes as society does. It would be, therefore, naive to expect the existence of only one literary theory. Literary theory does not only redefine the meaning of literature, but it also redefines its relationship with society. Literature is a product of society and so is literary theory. It changes as the needs of society change. In order to better understand this concept of dependence and change, let see when and how literary theory was born.

Literary theory is a relatively new phenomenon, but its beginnings date far back. Some say that Aristotle’s *Poetics* is an early example of literary theory; to some extent, I agree with that. It is not the kind of literary theory we know today, but it certainly had a great influence. In other words:

Literary theory and the formal practice of literary interpretation runs a parallel but less well known course with the history of philosophy and is evident in the historical record at least as far back as Plato. (Brewton 2015)

Literary theory as a strictly new phenomenon started in 1950. As such, it disregards previous aesthetic theories and the influence they had on the creation of literary theory. To state that literary theory started in 1950s would be true only of modern literary theory, but not the broad aspect of it.

To fully understand the history of literary theory, and to understand why did it emerged in the first place, it is necessary to travel back in time and investigate the state of society at the time of the birth of literary theory.

In his book, *Literary Theory: An Introduction*, Terry Eagleton dedicates a chapter to the rise of English. He explains social aspects that contributed to a new look on the English literature from which, later on, literary theory emerged. The number one reason for the new look was a bloody civil war that set the social classes at each other's throats. The book *The Rules of Art*, written by Pierre Bourdieu, speaks of similar issues. On one side there is the ruling aristocracy and on the other the middle class. In order to bring some peace and understating between the two opposites, literature gained a new importance. Literature included institutions such as periodicals and coffee houses (Eagleton 1996, 15). It became a crucial, irreplaceable part of human life and political side of society. It became an ideology:

English was an arena in which the most fundamental questions of human existence – what is meant to be a person, to engage in significant relationship with others, to live from the vital centre of the most essential values – were thrown into vivid relief and made the object of the most intensive scrutiny. (Eagleton 1996, 27)

Since the meaning of literature in society became so powerful, it was only a question of time before literature would take a new turn. Being discussed in coffee houses, published in periodicals and fought on and on by oppositions about what is considered to be literature and what not, was no longer enough. Literature needed a new place, a new arena in which it would finally blossom into a perfect rose. The next stop was universities.

The struggles of literature, in our case English literature, to become an accepted and respected subject at the universities were not easy. It was frowned upon by other scholars and regarded as a subject that does not hold water. This was probably the reason why scholars started to speak up and write down their thoughts about what they thought literature is, creating small but sure steps towards modern literary theory. On the other hand, it may be that every subject worth being thought at the university needs a theory of it. Whichever holds true, one thing is sure. Literature proved its worth and it did not only take a place among university subjects, but it took the place.

In a highly scientific and materialistic society, literature, a complete opposite, fought its way up. It could not completely escape the influence of such society. Literary theory consists of different schools, and the very first schools went hand in hand with

materialistic and scientific society. The analytical approach used in science was transferred to literary theory. It was the time of great scientific discoveries, so it is not strange that the influence of it can be seen in the literary theory itself. Although, at that time many literary schools existed, their basis was pretty much the same. They were all the product of a well-connected society.

Later on, as the progress of society went on and literature started to change, so did the methods of literary theory. Literary theory underwent the change from highly scientific oriented and strict methods to rather relativistic methods of interpreting literature.

Let us take a look at a few representatives of two extremes and literary theory in general.

Formalism

Formalism is a literary theory school that places “the study of literature on a scientific basis through objective analysis of the motifs, devices, techniques, and other ‘functions’ that comprise the literary work” (Brewton 2015). Its beginnings date back to early 1920s when it rose as an antithesis to Romanticism, which place an artist, individual creative genius, at the centre of attention. In formalists’ eyes it was about time to bring the text back to the spotlight.

The main subject of formalist analysis is a structural purpose of text. As the name itself implies, formalist were preoccupied with literary form. “Form was the content” (Brewton 2015). Since formalism is a “study of literature on a scientific basis” (Brewton 2015), it had its own set of rules for objective analysis of texts. This is why the main preoccupation of formalist was literary form, but literary form with all its intrinsic features that combine grammar, syntax and, probably the most important, literary devices.

In practice, formalist analysis of the text looked pretty much like this: a particular text was taken into account; any cultural or historical connotations were then peeled off and disregarded until only a pure form was left. This form was carefully dissected and bare literary devices were left. Formalists analyzed these literary devices and compared them to already analyzed literary devices of other works. Only text was important. Text’s historical, cultural or biographical context lost its importance.

Emerging from the 1920s, “a prolific period for new inventions and improvements to existing technology that had a major impact on the way people lived” (1920-30.co 2015), formalism was highly influenced by society. This is best seen in its determination to leave society out of its analysis. In a modern, industrial life with alienating tendencies, formalism took the alienating approach of modern science to analyse texts and thus counter society itself.

Structuralism

Structuralism is a literary theory school which argues that the ‘literary banter of a text’ lies only in new structure and not in the specifics of character development and voice. The beginnings of structuralism’s prominence can be traced back to the era of French existentialism, particularly 1960s. Structuralism rejects human freedom and choice and emphasises the importance of structures that determine human experience and life. More specifically, there is a larger structure inside which parts of human culture are understood by their relationship to the greater structure.

Some consider structuralism to be an extension of literary school called formalism, while others believe formalism to be structuralism’s predecessor. Whichever one believes is right, one thing is certain: both structuralism and formalism approach literature in a purely scientific way, putting the study of literature on an objective basis.

Another very important thing is to understand why structuralism operates as it does, is to understand its root in linguistics. The ideas of Ferdinand de Saussure, a Swiss linguist, that the underlying structure of signification is more important than the meaning itself are transferred to the analysis of literature.

In literary theory, structuralist criticism relates literary texts to a larger structure, which may be a particular genre, a range of intertextual connections, a model of a universal narrative structure, or a system of recurrent patterns or motifs. (Barry 2002)

In other words, everything written is regulated by specific literature.

Structuralism, successor of formalism and Saussure’s linguistic, and predecessor of semiotics, the philosophical theory of signs and symbols, continues the tradition of

objective, alienating approach to literature. It is no strange for it to do so being prominent in the time of existentialism. The interest in individual and its freedom is counterbalanced by structuralism's interest in structure. Structuralism is a strict system with even more strict rules.

Post-structuralism

Post-structuralism is a criticism of structuralism and its close system that no longer works in a postmodernist society. The "reference to an empirically certifiable reality is no longer guaranteed by language" (Brewton 2015).

The term itself was forged by American academics having in mind the heterogeneous works that had their international prominence in 1960s and 1970s. The movement was less unified than previous movements such as formalism and structuralism was. Approaches that fall under the name of post-structuralism are: Deconstruction, Reader response theory, Reception theory and Gender theory.

Two prominent names of post-structuralism are Roland Barthes, a French literary theorist, and Michel Foucault, a French philosopher and historian. Roland Barthes was a key figure concerning the division between structuralism and post-structuralism, while Michael Foucault had a critical influence on a creation of postmodern perspective. According to Foucault, there are concrete historical situations in which knowledge is created from the form of discourse. "Knowledge is not communicated by discourse but is discourse itself, can only be encountered textually" (Brewton 2015).

Although post-structuralism is a heterogeneous movement, there are still some common grounds present in each of approaches. The most evident one is the importance of the meaning that the reader perceives. This leads to multi-interpretations of one single text, or as deconstructionists would put it, "endless deferral of meaning, a system of differences between units of language that has no resting place or final signifier that would enable the other signifiers to hold their meaning" (Brewton 2015).

Some criticize post-structuralism as being too relativistic, while others criticize its extremity and linguistic complexity. Some see post-structuralism as a threat to traditional values and their high position of the only true scholarly standard. But, what

else to expect from the movement that is highly related to postmodernism and sceptical look on everything society has to offer? In a sceptical and re-evaluating society it was only a question of time when someone will start to rethink even the solid, stable, self-sufficient structure introduced by predeceasing formalists and structuralists. The structure was no longer enough. Both literature and human life strived for a re-evaluation and different interpretations according to either class, type of society, race, gender or age.

Reader response theory

As the name itself implies, reader response theory is a literary theory school that focuses on the reader and his experience of a literary work. The beginnings of reader response theory date back to 1960s and 1970s US and Germany, the same time when post-structuralism came to power. Reader response theory, although taught as a part of post-structuralism, is interesting on its own.

According to reader response theory, the reader acts as an active agent in creating the meaning of a literary work. In other words, literature is a performing act, and the reader is the medium. Each reader rediscovers the meaning of the work. New reader = new interpretation and new meaning. Tyson explains this in the following way:

[...] reader-response theorists share two beliefs: 1) that the role of the reader cannot be omitted from our understanding of literature and 2) that readers do not passively consume the meaning presented to them by an objective literary text; rather they actively make the meaning they find in literature. (Eagleton 1996, 154)

One of the most prominent representatives of reader response theory is Stanley Fish, and American literary theorist. In his book, *Is There a Text in This Class? The Authority of Interpretive Communities*, Fish explains his stance on literary criticism and establishes his reader response theory. Just like every other representative of reader response theory, Fish sets the reader as the most important part of interpretation process. Our reading or experience of the text is what makes constitutes the meaning, the temporal nature of reading. By this he goes against everything formalism stands for. What is more, he claims that the formal features are

interpretation themselves and cannot be used as a basis for any legitimate interpretation.

Denying at the same time that the meaning is in the text and using the text to control reader's experience can be troubling. Luckily, Fish came up with an answer to this by proposing that the reader actually makes the text by bringing assumptions to it. That, however, does not mean that reader can make up any meaning. It simply means that the text is always set, and it is set for a way of reading and in the time of reading it can change.

The question of stability and consistency of interpretation stands out. Fish finds the solution for both stability and variety of interpretation in something that is prior to interpretative acts. What is prior is the reader's interpretative strategy. In other words, we choose to read the work in particular way, although we do not have to. This is excellently explained by introducing the notion of interpretive communities.

Interpretive communities are made of those readers who share interpretative strategies for writing texts. The meaning of the text is brought to it by the reader and it changes depending on the community to which the reader belongs.

According to Fish, everything is always in a context and it is because of this context that texts have meaning. Analysing structure is not a wrong approach, but it does not suffice. Broader interpretation of the text is needed.

Fish's reader response theory as well as formalism will prove to be important, if not crucial, in later analysis. The two of them go together like chalk and cheese and this unthinkable linkage is what makes the perfect match. In formalism the distinction between literary and non-literary text is crucial, since the object of analysis is the text itself, more specifically the analysis of its form. On the other hand, reader response theory does not deal only with literary texts. It applies the tools of textual interpretation to non-literary texts as well as the life itself. This crucial difference comes from the fact that neither formalism nor reader response theory derives its criticism from the same intellectual tradition. The vastly different traditions, cultures, societies, eras or whatever you feel like calling it, create the differences between schools of literary theory. The objectives and goals of various heterogeneous literary theory schools are not as important as the fact that all of them have deeply rooted cultural grounds.

Both Terry Eagleton and Pierre Bourdieu talk about the importance society has regarding art. Their views are a bit different. Terry Eagleton, in his book *Literary Theory: An Introduction*, takes on a more simple, semi-chronological approach. He discusses the topic of the importance of society and art through a sort of historical overview of literary theory. Pierre Bourdieu, on the other hand, discusses the topic more from economic and political point in his book *The Rules of Art*. He discusses how political and economic changes affected the change in literature.

Eagleton and Bourdieu adopt a different approach of interpreting the relationship between society and literature, Eagleton having almost the historical approach of cultural anthropology and Bourdieu a more down-to-earth politically-economical approach, but their main idea remains the same. That idea is that society plays a special and important role when it comes to literature, its development and interpretation. Society creates the need for stories. Humans write them, give them special status, decode them, interpret them and either store them for the next generation or throw them out of the window. All we do and all we are is conditioned by the society we live in, and so is literature.

To better understand this notion a short examination of hermeneutics follows. Hermeneutics is a theory of interpretation and as such covers various historical and philosophical eras reaching far back to ancient Greek philosophy. Modern hermeneutics, especially the hermeneutics of Martin Heidegger's student Hans-Georg Gadamer, stresses the importance of different cultural and historical context when interpreting and reading literature. Different new meanings arrive from different cultural and historical contexts.

All interpretation is situational, shaped and constrained by the historically relative criteria of a particular culture; there is no possibility of knowing the literary text 'as it is'. (Eagleton 1996, 62)

This way of perceiving the interpretation of literature is quite similar to post-structuralists' ideas. To be exact, reception theory, a version of reader response theory, is the most recent development of hermeneutics. It seems that no matter which approach we take, there is no escaping the hand of society.

Animals and stories

2.1. Fables

What pops into our mind when we hear the word fable? Is it shortness? Or a moral lesson? Or animals that talk? No matter which of these you find yourself thinking about, they are all true. Fable is one of the oldest forms of folk literature; it has survived many changes and shakes human lives even today. This brief allegorical narrative that comes either in verse or in prose and teaches valuable moral lessons, endured so long with the help of its special trait – animals.

These animals are not just any random animals but living, speaking, anthropomorphized animals. Their role is to tell a story that illustrates a moral thesis and satirizes human beings. One may ask how come such serious matters as moral and life lessons are trusted upon animals. The answer is a simple one. Animals can teach people valuable lessons because when reading or hearing a story involving animals, people become amused without becoming defensive. The simplicity and straightforwardness of animals involved makes people relax and open their mind to any moral advice fables have to offer. This is the reason why fables have been present in human life for so long.

The Panchatantra, a collection of fables in Sanskrit, is considered to hold one of the first fables ever written. Some even say that Aesop's fables had their start in India. No matter which holds true, it is certain that fables existed for a very long time and that their importance, in different cultures and countries, is a strong one.

In ancient India and China fables have been a part of a larger frame. Fables, and especially their moral stories, had been used as a tool for providing an emphasis or clarification of a point. Later on, during Aesop's time, fables seem to stand on their own, without serving as an emphasis tool of any sort or being intrinsically connected to each other. This may have been the result of the different way Chinese, Indian and Greek societies were formed, or it may be that people were just unable to see the broader picture of Aesop's fables. Aesop's fables might have

The modern society seems to have forgotten about fables, except for those who study either anthropology or literature, but fables have endured and are present as ever. By that I do not mean Jean de La Fontaine's famous fables or James Thurber's *Fables of Our Time*. When I say that fables are all around us I mean that they have

taken on many different forms and are, at the first glance, almost unrecognizable, yet very much present.

The fables have been used in so many different children's books that it is hard to pick just one as an example. Felix Salten's *Bambi*, today almost a must story to tell a child, is one example. Another example is a collection of stories, *The Adventures of Andy Ant*, from which a child learns important moral truths by reading about the friendship and adventures of a little ant and his human friend Joey. Animals are considered to be a simple way for a child to relate and learn the most basic life lessons (which should not come as a surprise, considering fables' long history).

However, fables are not used only in children's books but are also part of in modern adult literature. Some examples of it are *The Revolt*, a metaphor for the Bolshevik Revolution of 1917 written by Wladyslaw Reymont and Juan and Victor Ataucuri Garcia's book *Peruvian Fables*, a collection of myths, legends and beliefs of Andean and Amazonian Peru in a shape of fables.

Fables are again a part of broader and diverse frameworks. They are no longer admired only for their simplicity, shortness and use of animals. They play an important role of providing people with valuable life lessons while at the same time making their life lighter by bringing.

Two examples that use animals as their main characters follow. Examples will not be analyzed in depth since they are only transitional examples that pave the way to the number one example of the thesis, *Life of Pi*, and connect it with previous chapters. The transitional examples are *Animal Farm* and *Tainaron: Mail From Another City*. They are seemingly incompatible examples of literature but their core is the same, as is the core of *Life of Pi*. By analysing these two examples, each with different literary theory method, the importance of animals in literature, fable-like structure, and the use of the two to create allegory resulting in criticism of society become evident.

2.2. *Animal Farm*

Animal Farm is a story written by George Orwell in a period between November 1943 to February 1944 and was first published in England on 17 August 1945. It is a marvellous story about animals on a farm and their revolt against men, taking form of a novel.

The story itself is constructed of ten chapters with a conventional narrative structure. From the first to the last chapter the narrator traces and tells the events of rise and decline of the Animal revolution in its chronological order. Each chapter slowly builds up the story and tension. The first several chapters open gently, while those closer to the end “open by referring to the suffering of the animals or the harsh winters (Chapters 5, 6 and 7 all open in this way) and end with the gradual perversion of one of the Commandments” (Opalinska 1997, 62). What is more, after the introduction is set and the climax is built, the story takes on a rapid pace ending the plot in only several pages.

This kind of structure is a typical narrative structure followed by a typical pace – slightly longer introduction to the subject of the story, build up of a climax, the climax itself and, finally, a downward spiral to the end. The pace and the structure coexist and the repetition of some structures adds to the importance of pace. Some repeated parts are Major’s speech from the beginning of the novel, the song ‘Beasts of England’ – “Beasts of every land and clime, / Hearken to my joyful tidings / Of the golden future time” (Orwell 2008, 7) – and dogs and sheep bleating.

All repeated parts serve as a connection between the beginning of the book, its middle and end, but they also serve as an emphasis. By repeating something over and over again, the repeated thing becomes emphasised and its importance clear, as is the case with the repeated breaking of the Commandments.

The Commandments are broken one by one: the animals remember one rule, for example “No animal shall sleep in a bed” (Orwell 2008, 15); they say it out loud, the pigs tell them that they remember the rule differently than it actually is, the animals check the wall, they find out that the pigs were right and that the rule is “No animal shall sleep in a bed with sheets” (Orwell 2008, 45), and so on and on. Eventually, the animals completely give up and do not remember the rules any more, do not say them out loud and do not check the wall. By repeating one process, the importance of the repeated item is emphasised and one cannot but see it.

In the same way the structure, pace, repetition and emphasis are connect, so is the language used. The language used is simple, without any ornaments. Sentences are short. Words are also short. All in all, the language is straightforward, clear and terse, which makes it fresh and interesting: “Windmill or no windmill, [Boxer] said, life would go on as it had always gone on – that is, badly” (Orwell 2008, 34).

Orwell combined misleading simplicity of structure and language with other literary devices such as repetition and emphasis to create a story that is “as technically perfect as any creative writing can be” (Brodie’s Notes 1963, 53). The story is, as most agree, fable-like. Orwell’s simple and straightforward storyline as well as the use of animals make it approachable and readable to the widest audience, while actually being “a veiled criticism of the regime of the Soviet Union” (Opalinska 1997, 8). By using a fable-like structure, “a story with a message and meaning in which animals act as if they were humans” (Brodie’s Notes 1963, 20), Orwell creates a perfect ground for allegory.

2.3. *Tainaron: Mail From Another City*

Leena Krohn's novel *Tainaron: Mail From Another City* is a science fiction/fantasy epistolary novel. In it the protagonist, through a collection of letters, explains to her friend her stay in a bug city. The novel itself consists of 30 letters. The letters are short and poem-like prose and "seem to enjoy an independence that is typical in collections of short stories rather than in novels" (Lyytikäinen 2012, 27). The only thing that seemingly holds them together is a passive protagonist, the narrator and the sender of the letters.

Although each chapter could be read on its own and interpreted on its own, complete and deep interpretation of the novel is possible only when letters are looked at as a unity. This is a hard quest since the atypical novel structure and use of sci-fi-like fantasy stand opposite to Leena Krohn's serious style and tendency to fabulate. The latter leads us to consider the fact that the novel draws its elements from "the tradition of satirical allegory" (Lyytikäinen 2012, 25), while the former brings Leena Krohn's writing "closer to the allegorical trends in postmodern writing" (Lyytikäinen 2012, 25).

The novel is an allegory of a modern way of life and harsh criticism of the same. In each episode, in each letter, one can find several different metaphors. The most obvious one is the use of insect-people, intertwined specie between an insect and a human. Krohn uses insects because she believes insects to be "the animal order that is most strange and estranging to humans" (Lyytikäinen 2012, 30), and thus ideal "to reflect the estrangement of human beings from one another" (Lyytikäinen 2012, 30).

Other metaphors and possible interpretations of the novel are: estrangement in modern cities; metamorphosis as a metaphor for ever changing idea of identity, juxtaposing a classical idea of identity with a postmodern one, and reincarnation as a metaphor of spiritual search in postmodern society. No matter which interpretation of the novel you find true, "all the images are metaphors referring to the same allegorical meaning" (Lyytikäinen 2012, 28) – a harsh criticism of postmodern society and its estrangement towards everything including people's own identity.

2.4. What do fable, *Animal Farm* and *Tainaron* have in common?

One may ask what possibly could a classic novel, a postmodern novel and a literary genre have in common. The answer is a lot. I will start by exploring the differences and, later, similarities of these three seemingly incompatible cases.

Neither *Animal Farm* nor *Tainaron* were analyzed in depth, yet the main differences between them are obvious. *Animal Farm* is considered to be one of the classics and is definitely a more traditional novel than *Tainaron*, which is considered to be a nice example of postmodern novel. What makes *Animal Farm* a representative of traditional literature and *Tainaron* a part of postmodern literature?

First of all, *Animal Farm* has a typical narrative structure – introduction, development, climax, resolution and end. This typical narrative structure creates the need and space for other literary devices, such as repetition, which are further emphasised by the use of a simple and straightforward language. Moreover, the different chapters are connected to each other by one simple plot which, only when looked at as a package, create a story.

In contrast, *Tainaron* is composed of 30 different, almost individual letters connected only by the same protagonist acting as a narrator. The language used is lyrical and hard to read – “The hustling forest of antennae and pedipalpi in the streets at rush-hour is certainly an extraordinary sight for people like us [...]” (Khron 2004, 33) – leaving novel readable only to a limited amount of people. Style and images are sci-fi and fantasy-like, making the story even more limited and anti-broad audience like.

However, it is not only the structure, style and language that make a work of art traditional or postmodern. Its background plays a crucial role in defining art. Having this in mind, it is no wonder George Orwell’s *Animal Farm* is so different from Leena Krohn’s *Tainaron*. The very fact that one novel is a piece of English literature and the other of Finnish literature solves one part of the mystery. English and Finnish literature, although both part of western literature, are fundamentally different. Their history and culture are different and so is their literature.

The main difference, however, is not so much the difference between English and Finnish culture, as is the fact that *Animal Farm* was written during the Second World War when the alliance with the Soviet Union was at its highest, and *Tainaron* was written a lot later, in 1985. George Orwell’s disagreement with the high position Stalin held in the eyes of the British people and intelligentsia led him to write a criticism that

is marvellously disguised as a traditional novel with typical narrative structure and simple language. On the other hand, Leena Krohn is a Finnish author that studied philosophy and also mostly writes about man's relationship with the world and himself, especially exploring the borders between reality and illusion as one of the prime problems of a modern world. Therefore, it is not strange that she takes the liberty of using a unique dream-like style when approaching such delicate issues of a modern man. Orwell had to use straightforward, simple structure and language for his criticism to be interpreted just as he wrote it, while Krohn had to use the complexity of style, a thin line between fantasy and reality, to show the severity of modern life problems.

These chronological and cultural differences create the first similarity between *Animal Farm* and *Tainaron*. Both Orwell and Krohn looked for the right tools, either structure like or style like, to convey the delicate topics. What is more, both Orwell and Krohn used animals to bring their criticisms of society to a new level. Orwell used animals' simplicity and straightforwardness to further stress the simplicity of his structure and language, but also to veil his true intentions in fable-like fairy tale. Krohn, however, used animals to further stress the grandioseness of estrangement of modern life. In both cases, animals served as a number one tool for making stories moral-like. This way an old literary form was brought back to life.

Fable is a very old literary form which has changed drastically through the course of history. The fable's simple Aesop-like structure is no longer present in the same extent as it once was but fable remains alive and influential. By taking on different structures and by becoming a crucial part of different genres of different parts of literary history, fable once again lives up to its old glory. It is a part of a broader framework and helps to prove and illustrate a point. In Orwell's and Krohn's case, fable does not only prove a point, but creates a marvellous fairy tale-like world serving as basis for interpreting the novels as satirical allegories of the world we live in. Orwell's *Animal Farm* is not just an allegory of Stalinism, but a satirical allegory about the abuse of power. Krohn's *Tainaron* is a satirical allegory about "the moral flaws of individuals or society as a whole" (Lyytikäinen 2012, 36).

George Orwell's *Animal Farm* and Leena Krohn's *Tainaron: Mail From Another City* and their connection to fable lifted the dust from the importance of animals in the literature. The times of placing fantasy and science fiction literature in a separate basket, far away from any real literature under pretence that fantasy and sci-fi have

nothing to do with the reality, are behind us. Considering only one literary approach to be correct when tackling the problem of analysing and interpreting a work of art has long gone. Both formalist analysis of *Animal Farm* and more reader response analysis of *Tainaron* lead to the same conclusion. In fact, it was the combination of the two that did the work.

Now that transitional examples have been analysed, the connection between fable-like structure and the importance of animals in creating allegory that results in criticism of society has been established, the analysis of *Life of Pi* follows. In order for the analysis to be successful, it is necessary to place *Life of Pi* inside a specific literature and establish the importance of animals in literature that reaches beyond fable and the two transitional examples.

Life of Pi

3.1. Canadian literature and animals

Canadian literature is literature that has its origins in Canada, whether written in English or French. Much like any other literature, Canadian literature has its socio-political context and is influenced by it. However, Canadian literature is not only sociologically-oriented literature. The influences are broad both in historical as well as geographical sense, resulting in a variety of genres.

Since the scope of Canadian literature is so wide, it is often divided into different sub-categories making it easier to speak of or research. Whether it is written in English or French, from this region or that province, by this author or that author some themes and traits are common to them all. For instance, Canadian literature often reflects its perspective on Canada's position in the world, frontier life and nature.

Nature is a recurring theme in Canadian literature. Its portrayal ranges from a beautiful portrayal of a divine life force to naturalistic portrayal of a raw and cruel human enemy. Both admiration and respect bordering with awe are present, which is not strange considering the extraordinary beauty of nature's power.

What is more, Canadian literature does not deal only with nature as a general concept. A recurring theme of Canadian literature is animals. From the earliest days, right up to the present, animals have had a special position in Canadian literature. For example, Ernest Thompson Seton and Sir Charles Roberts both wrote about animals.

Margaret Atwood was one of the first critics to investigate and write about the phenomenon of recurring animal themes in Canadian literature. She has done that in 1968 in her poetry collection *The Animals in That Country*, where she highlighted the "curious dichotomy of mankind's relationship with nature" (Ghosh 2015) and later, in 1971, in her critical study *Survival: A Thematic Guide to Canadian Literature*, where she devotes a chapter to animal stories. However, these are not her only works in which Atwood deals with animals and, especially, our relationship to them. Through her work she repeatedly made observations about our relationship towards animals, pointing out the interdependence between man and animals.

Although Margaret Atwood seems to be a pioneer on the subject of animals in Canadian literature, being one of the first critics to openly address the topic, many

Canadian writers wrote about animals. To fully grasp the importance of animals in Canadian literature it is important to travel back to the time of Ernest Thompson Seton and Sir Charles Roberts. The two are remembered for their part in creating the one distinctively Canadian genre – the animal story.

In that time, animals as characters were depicted as accurately as they could be. Seton's stories "are not about animals that are humanized beyond recognition (as in the folk and fairy tale tradition); rather, his animal characters are demonstrably real" (Sandlos 200, 76). By portraying animals as real as possible Seton emphasizes the importance of realism and natural history adding value to "the idea that the observation and contemplation of animal behavior may somehow lead to new human values" (Sandlos 2000, 82). Both Seton and Roberts made their animal characters authentic, and both authors saw the importance animal stories have when dealing with either human cruelty towards animals or human alienation from nature.

The uniqueness of the realism of animal story was later recognized by Margaret Atwood. She takes a step forward from Seton and Roberts's view on animals. Unlike the two of them, who "were more concerned about writing accurate natural history – stories that reflect the habits and behaviors of real animals within a fictional frame – than with creating political allegories (like those of Orwell) out of the basic material of animal lives" (Sandlos 2000, 75), Atwood sees animals, their suffering and dying as a "direct reflection of the nation's deepest cultural anxieties" (Sandlos 2000, 74). In other words, animals are us.

In more recent times, animals are still present in Canadian literature and various efforts of different authors to create fiction from basic material of animal lives are still successful. Actually, the position of animals in Canadian literature became such an interesting topic that in May 2005 the University of Ottawa organized a conference "The Animals in This Country" as a part of their annual Canadian literature symposia. At this conference various important issues concerning the roles animals play in Canadian literature were discussed. Later, based on this symposium, Janice Fiamengo created a book *Other Selves: Animals in the Canadian Literary Imagination*.

It seems that animals have always been and will be a crucial part of Canadian literature. The importance of animals in literature in general was already explored in the previous chapter, which, together with this brief history of importance of animals in Canadian literature, makes for a compelling subject. Animals have been a part of

human life from its very beginning. They provided us with food, clothes and company. Human lives and animal lives are ever interlaced the same way as literature has always been in a coexistence with society. Therefore, it is only natural for artists to combine the three to create the never ending roundabout. Be it fable, allegory, satire, naturalism, realism, fantasy, folk tradition or sci-fi, the story with animals in central position serves a higher purpose – it educates us about animals, nature and, in the end, about ourselves.

3.2. *Life of Pi* – analysis part 1

Life of Pi is a Canadian novel written by Yann Martel, a Canadian author born in Spain, with a degree in philosophy. After being rejected by several publishing houses, the work was finally published in 2001. The rough start did not diminish its worth, and the novel won several prizes, one of which is Man Booker Prize for Fiction. Later, in 2012, it was adapted into a movie which also won several awards, such as Golden Globe Award for Best Original Score and Best Achievement in Directing at the 85th Academy Awards.

The novel has to offer far more than mere prizes and awards. The story it tells is “a story that will make you believe in God” (Martel 2012, XIII). Whether this statement is true or not it is up to you but, nonetheless, *Life of Pi* is one of a kind. Its structure, language, narrative, setting and objective are close to brilliant. It starts as a story about a boy whose name is Piscine Molitor, otherwise known as Pi, but ends up to be a story about his survival of a harrowing shipwreck. He survives 227 days on a lifeboat, which would be amazing all on its own, but he survives that in a company of a grown up Bengal tiger named Richard Parker.

Their voyage and adventures in the open sea make the novel an adventure story somewhat similar to either *Robinson Crusoe* by Daniel Defoe and *The Old Man and the Sea* by Ernest Hemingway. However, the structure of the novel is not simple, and its plot can be tackled in many different ways. This brings out the fact that the novel itself was classified very differently. Most people see it as an adventure story (Jordan 2002) due to the shipwreck and survival on the open sea, and such a classification is the most straightforward one. Some see it as a post-colonial novel, since it focuses on the culture and stories of India, a former British colony. This kind of classification leaves out many important parts of the novel, such as Pi’s growing up and becoming a man by surviving the shipwreck, which is why the novel is also classified as a Bildungsroman (Kidd 2013). Others, who tend to focus more on how the novel was written rather than on what was written, see it as magic/fantastic realism and fable-like story resembling Aesop’s fables. And lastly, many see it as allegory, or at least an allegorical storytelling (Krist 2002).

In some way, all these classifications are true, and yet, all of them leave something out. To see what such classifications include and what do they leave out, the novel

has to be analyzed. The type of analysis suitable for determining the genre of the novel and its real objective is formalist analysis. Formalists focus on structural elements and artistic techniques in order to determine the content. Neither the author's nor the work's background is important, only the work itself.

Structure

Life of Pi is a story within a story – the story of shipwreck and survival inside the story of a young boy named Pi. The book is divided into two parts, the preface and the novel. The novel itself is divided into three parts. These three parts are divided into 100 chapters.

However, although the preface, titled “Author’s Note,” seems at the first read to be just that – a few pages long author’s note – it is not really. The autobiographic resemblance is there but it is not present throughout the whole “Author’s Note”. Yann Martel surely wrote books before he wrote *Life of Pi*, and he might have been in the dreadful process of investigating and writing a new book but it is unlikely that he met a man who told him the story that will make us believe in god. This is why I find it important to re-examine the structure.

The novel has a tripartite structure. The first part is the “Author’s Note” – the Author’s story about how he came to know about Pi’s existence and his story. The second part is the story about Pi’s life, and the third story is the story of shipwreck and survival, more precisely, about Pi and Richard Parker. It is crucial to mention that the second part, the story of Pi’s life, naturally follows and is born from the first part; therefore the second part is a story within the first part. Similarly, the third part, the story of shipwreck and survival, is one big and important part of Pi’s life story; therefore, the third part is a story within the second part, but also the first. Simply said, *Life of Pi* is not a story within a story, but a story within a story within a story.

Diagram 1: Story within a story within a story

This kind of structure division may sound complicated, so it would be useful to see what kind of role each part plays.

Firstly, the “Author’s Note” acts like an introduction to the book’s supposed origins and sets the frame of the novel. It acts as a non-fictional part which blurs the line between fiction and fact (real life), taking us to the magical world of Pi’s life.

Pi’s childhood and life up until the shipwreck acts as a setting for, as many people perceive it, the main story – the shipwreck and survival. Themes covered in this part play an important role in Pi’s survival. The two main themes are the true nature of animals and religion.

The shipwreck and, mostly, the survival part of the novel is the main part and the main plot of the whole novel. It is true that in this part the most horrible and the most beautiful things happen, but its plot would not have the weight it has without the introductions made by the previous parts. Only combined parts make the story what it truly is.

The second and third part of the novel take a form of a memoir divided into 100 chapters. The division on 100 chapters is kind of strange since the structure of these 100 chapters varies drastically. Some chapters are only a sentence long, for example chapter 75:

On the day when I estimated it was Mother’s birthday, I sang ‘Happy Birthday’ to her out loud. (Martel 2012, 282)

Other chapters seem to have no end. The Chapters have no consistency of form and length, but they are all complete and contained. Variations contribute to other literary devices such as tone, style and narration, while the division on 100 chapters makes rational sense of things – makes order of disordered journey.

The structure of the chapters varies and so does the sentence structure. Some sentences, especially in the second part when explaining Pi's early life, are lengthy, well-structured and extremely detailed. Like this one explaining the magnificent Krishna:

She sees in Krishna's mouth the whole complete entire universe, all the stars and planets of space and the distance between them, all the lands and seas of the earth and the life in them; she sees all the days of yesterday and all the days of tomorrow; she sees all ideas and all emotions, all pity and all hope, and the three strands of matter; nor a pebble, candle, creature village or galaxy is missing, including herself and every bit of dirt in its truthful place. (Martel 2012, 73)

Meanwhile, the sentences in the third part are shorter and not as detailed, sometimes bordering with empty and vague. For example, a sentence Pi wrote while being stranded on a life boat with Richard Parker:

They would go to improving the raft. I noticed in passing a smell. It was not the sharp smell of cat piss. It was vomit. (Martel 2012, 204)

Lastly, throughout the novel there are a few intrusions by the Author. They seem to be out of place and to disturb the ideally planed structure, but are in fact crucial parts of ideally planed structure. By recalling Author's voice, pauses are made and small bits of clarity and realism are restored.

All in all, the structure is carefully planned and carried out. It makes a sound basis for the plot, and acts as a fertile ground for other literary devices. It is a promising start of a great story.

Language, style and tone

The structure of the novel makes a promising start of an interesting story but the structure is only an empty shell which needs to be filled up with words to fulfil the starting promise. This is where literary devices such as language, style and tone come through.

All these devices are fairly connected to each other and to the structure, so it is only natural to analyse them together. The language used varies alongside the structure of the novel, its chapters and sentences. In general, it is colourful, concrete and casual. The first part of the novel differs slightly from the second and third part but only as much as to create the distinction between narrators. Here is an example of the relaxed language used in the first part:

So I flew to Bombay. This is not so illogical if you realize three things: that a stint in India will beat the restlessness out of any living creature; that a little money can go a long way there; and that a novel set in Portugal in 1939 may have very little to do with Portugal in 1939. (Martel 2012, IX)

The second part, Pi's life up until the shipwreck, is full of detailed descriptions, rich and colourful vocabulary, which gives the concreteness necessary to take Pi's life seriously. Slight difference in the language used in the first part and the language used in the second part contributes to the veracity of the second part while, at the same time, allowing the emphasis of stylistic language, which preserves the beauty and lightness of Pi's childhood, for example, Pi's love for swimming:

It was on my own, a guilty pleasure, that I returned to the sea, beckoned by the mighty waves that crushed down and reached for me in humble tidal ripples, gentle lassos that caught their willing Indian boy. (Martel 2012, 12)

The language used is truly beautiful and creates a special atmosphere which, by some standards, would count as unbelievable. Some instances in which details and richness of vocabulary go too far are parts when Pi talks about and describes different religions and his experience of them. Here is part of one such sentence:

[...] because of the whine of the reedy nadaswaram and the beating of drums, because of the fragrance of incense, because of flames of arati lamps circling

in the darkness, because of bhajans being sweetly sung, because of elephants standing around the bless, because of colourful murals telling colourful stories [...] (Martel 2012, 63)

After the shipwreck, which is described in simple, short sentences and words, the diversity of language takes a new shape. The structure and length of chapters and sentences starts to vary on a page basis. The words used are far more exact and concrete than they were before. The vocabulary loses its richness similarly as Pi's life loses its beauty, lightness and happy-go-luckiness. The language, or lack of it, defines Pi's changing moods and different stages of survival. At the very beginning, Pi's shock is presented through slight language decay. The language is direct, concise and without unnecessary details:

I looked about. Nothing but sea and sky. The same when we were on the top of a swell. (Martel 2012, 145)

Later, as the shock passes by and the decline of morale sets in, the language goes through yet another change becoming even shorter, including only his observations – the only thing keeping him alive:

Darkness came. There was no moon. Clouds hid the stars. The contours of things became hard to distinguish. Everything disappeared, the sea, the lifeboat, my own body. (Martel 2012, 156)

Pi's morale as well as the language used are restored by Pi's survival instinct. This is most evident when he talks about Richard Parker, since he uses storytelling techniques to describe him and his behaviour:

Tigers make a variety of sounds. They include a number of roars and growls, the loudest of these being most likely the full-throated aaonh, usually made during the mating season by males and oestrous females. It's a cry that travels far and wide, and is absolutely petrifying when heard close up. Tigers go woof when they are caught unawares [...] (Martel 2012, 217)

Interestingly, no matter how hard Pi tries to preserve his sane mind and language, either by writing a diary or having a constant monologue, his identity slowly floats away, creating space for daily routines only. The unexpected dialogue with a

Frenchman and a drastic shift in language, form and content, makes the plainness of language and the routine of daily struggle on the open sea ever more obvious. For a second, Pi's old identity, his culture, and the beauty and richness of conversation are restored; however, the sea takes it all back. The most obvious place in the dialogue where Pi's old culture and identity are seen for a split of a second is when the Frenchman makes a suggestion to eat meat and Pi finds himself shocked and repulsed by such a suggestion, although he himself has given up on being vegan:

"May I make a suggestion?"

"What?"

"Instead of coconut yam kootu, why not boiled beef tongue with a mustard sauce?"

"That sounds non-veg."

"It is. And then tripe."

"Tripe? You've eaten the poor animal's tongue and now you want to eat its stomach?" (Martel 2012, 329)

The final and the largest digression of language comes at the very end of the novel. After Pi is rescued, he is interviewed by Japanese officers about the shipwreck and his survival. This is the place in the story where the alternative, unimaginative, raw story of the shipwreck and survival is provided. The language used to convey this alternative is nothing more than yeastless facts. The language is simple and plain. The sentences are short and simple:

He clung to his life. At dawn he was still alive. He went in and out of consciousness. Mother gave him water. I caught sight of the amputated leg. It cut my breath short. In the commotion it had been shoved aside and forgotten in the dark. It had seeped a liquid and looked thinner. I took a life jacket and used it as a glove. I picked the leg up. (Martel 2012, 409-10)

This second version resembles and is a basis for the last chapter of the novel. The last chapter is actually the report Japanese officers wrote. The report is highly formal, concise and almost terse unlike anything else in the novel. Even shortness and plainness of Pi's language out in the open sea has more life's joy in it than this report:

Cause of sinking impossible to determine from available evidence. Standard insurance claim procedure for Oika. No further action required. Recommend the case be closed. (Martel 2012, 427)

Although the language differs from part to part and even inside one part, the language used in *Life of Pi* is colourful, rarely plain and full of life. This kind of language and a dynamic structure creates lively, picturesque, vivid, powerful, detailed and emotionally realistic style. In other words, the style of the novel is as spicy as Indian food. Once you taste it, you can never forget it. Its richness and fullness makes it unique.

Style's richness and diversity creates a unique voice. The fact that there are three different narrators, adds to uniqueness. The first narrator is The Author, not Yann Martel itself but a voice which is one of the characters in the story. Introducing The Author as a narrator is a traditional literary device that creates a layer of fallibility.

In most parts we have Pi, the first person subjective narrator, which gives the novel a sincere, yet fairy tale-like voice. The novel is cunningly given a reliable but dramatic voice by starting with a second person objective narrator, The Author, and ending with a third person narrator, the report.

The change of narrators, diversity in language, structure and voice, and spicy style, contribute to the tone of the novel. The tone is definitely earnest with serious but light undertone. It tells one that the story is true, that matters are, in fact, deadly serious, but that one should look at them and perceive them as lightly as possible, and focus one's attention to the beauty of it all and not ugliness, scariness and factualness.

The very structure of the novel sparks the promise of a great story, and language, style and tone of the novel proved it. What is more, the choice of words and narrators, as well as the style and tone, indicate that there is much more to the story than one might think after the first read.

Plot

The plot of the story are the events that make up the story. For plot to develop it is important to see how these events are linked together. The pattern by which events are related to each other creates the plot.

In the previous sections, the structure, language, style and tone of the novel were analysed. All these elements have one thing in common – they vary. The structure of the novel shows that the novel is created by combining at least three plots. The language used and the style and the tone of each part corroborate that, in fact, there are three different uses of language, three different styles, three different narrators and, therefore, three different plots.

However, the plots are not completely different and the structure proves that. The plots belong to each other and complement each other. Together they form one big plot. To determine how three plots create one, and what kind of a pattern this big plot takes, the pattern of each single plot has to be determined.

As said before, plot has some kind of a pattern. Each plot is different, so each plot has a different pattern, but the plot of a traditional novel is mostly presented as a triangle – exposition, rising action, climax, falling action and denouement.

Diagram 2: Diagram of a traditional plot

The plot of a traditional novel varies and so does the plot of *Life of Pi*. In order to explore and determine the overall plot, the plot of the third part will be explored first,

moving onto the second part and finally to the first part. After each part is covered the overall plot will be visible by adding the three plots together.

1. The third part

The third part is a story of shipwreck and survival. This story starts with a shipwreck explained in a very short terms. Almost as if the shipwreck itself is not important, but the sole story of survival.

The ship sank. It made a sound like a monstrous metallic burp. Things bubbled at the surface and then vanished. Everything was screaming: the sea, the wind, my heart. From the lifeboat I saw something in the water. (Martel 2012, 127)

For this reason the shipwreck itself could be taken as an exposition, an insertion of important background information. It is due to this exposition that one later knows what happened to Pi, how it happened and why he was the sole survivor except for the animal. This information does not only build some sort of a background, but contributes to the understanding of Pi's position and morale, or lack of it. The story later takes the reader through many ups and downs in Pi's morale, his struggle to survive and will to live. There are many possible instances which could count as a climax; however, there are only small victories in the long sequence of life's episodes Pi has to conquer.

Nonetheless, two instances strike out. One is the appearance of a carnivorous island. This episode, if the survival story is taken as a psychological Bildungsroman, would serve as the climax. There are few reasons why and the biggest one is that it was at this point that Pi almost completely lost his mind and, therefore, lost his battle for survival. But he did not.

I muttered, "Nothing but teeth left! TEETH!"

By the time morning came, my grim decision was taken. I preferred to set off and perish in search of my own kind than to live a lonely half-life of physical comfort and spiritual death on this murderous island. (Martel 2012, 380)

It was shortly after this episode that he reached the safety of Mexican coast. It was at this point that he realized how important it is for him to never give up and always push his limits in order to survive.

Another instance which could be marked as the climax is the farewell scene between Pi and Richard Parker. If Pi's story of survival is seen as a story of bringing together two juxtapositions – human and animal – and making peace between them, then his scene carries the most weight. Pi and Richard Parker reached the safety of the Mexican coast. One would think that their faiths are ever intertwined after everything they survived together, but one would be wrong, as Pi was. Richard Parker takes on his own path and disappears into the wild never to be seen again.

At the edge of the jungle, he stopped. I was certain he would turn my way. He would look at me. He would flatten his ears. He would growl. In some such way, he would conclude our friendship. He did nothing of the sort. He looked fixedly into the jungle. Then Richard Parker, companion of my torment, awful, fierce thing that kept me alive, moved forward and disappeared forever from my life. (Martel 2012, 382-83)

This is the climax of the story – the journey has ended and Pi is left to his own thoughts and plain cruelty of animal nature. Everything that kept him going was shattered in one simple second and the only thing left was life itself. His ideal partner, his co-spirit was forever gone.

No matter which of the two, or any other, instances you find to be the climax of the story, it is only important to notice that the story has the climax. The shipwreck acted as an exposition, many ups and downs acted as a rising action, leading to the climax of the story. What is left is the falling action and denouement. In this case, the two are the same. The actual falling action is so short that it can serve as a denouement. Pi is saved, he is in the hospital recovering and Japanese officers are there to hear his story to conclude the investigation of an unexplainable shipwreck.

All in all, the plot of the third part takes a shape of a traditional plot diagram – an uneven triangle.

Diagram 3: Third part's plot diagram

2. The second part

The second part of the novel starts by Pi telling a story, tracing back the steps of his life. He talks of himself and his life. It is mostly the story about his childhood and growing up back in India. He recalls all special events, all crucial lessons, but also all the small things that make childhood special, as his was. In this introduction through childhood, many important themes are introduced, making sound basis for what is yet to come. Some of these themes include the meaning of Pi's original name:

It was the only pool that made Mamaji fall silent, his memory making too many lengths to mention.

Mamaji remembered, Father dreamed.

That is how I got my name when I entered this world, a last, welcome addition to my family, three years after Ravi: Piscine Molitor Patel. (Martel 2012, 15),

but also his nickname; the origin of Richard Parker's name:

The hunter, whose name was Richard Parker, picked it up with his bare hands and, remembering how it had rushed to drink in the river, baptized it Thirsty. But the shipping clerk at the Howrah train station was evidently a man both befuddled and diligent. All the papers we received with the cub clearly stated that its name was Richard Parker, that the hunter's name was Thirsty and that his family name was None Given. Father had had a good chuckle over the mix-up and Richard Parker's name had stuck. (Martel 2012, 177);

the human-animal relations; religion and its importance in Pi's life and the socio-political background that led Pi's family to leave the country.

The socio-political background, which is the part of the introduction, may also serve as a rising action, resulting in Pi leaving India.

Mrs. Gandhi finally got the best of Father. In February 1976, the Tamil Nadu government was brought down by Delhi. It had been one of Mrs. Gandhi's most vocal critics. The takeover was smoothly enforced – Chief Minister Karunanidhi's ministry vanished quietly into "resignation" or house arrest – and what does the fall of one local government matter when the whole country's Constitution has been suspended these last eight months? But it was to Father the crowning touch in Mrs. Gandhi's dictatorial takeover of the nation. The camel at the zoo was unfazed, but that straw broke Father's back. (Martel 2012, 104)

The combination of pre-leaving events in India, preparing for the leave and leave itself prepare the reader for a new chapter in Pi's life. However, this chapter ends up being the unexpected one. Pi is preparing for a new life, new country, new school, new people and new approach to things and he does get a new approach to things, but unfortunate one. Everything changes. His so-far life and his to-be life change in one terrible second. The shipwreck takes from him everything he knew to be true and the sea takes the little of what is left.

Although the shipwreck is a twist that may act as a climax of Pi's so-far story, what follows cannot be perceived as a falling action, as a traditional novel plot would expect it. It is, rather, a new story with shipwreck serving as an introduction. The rest of it, the rising action, climax and falling action or denouement were already explained. It seems that the second part makes for one layer of the plot and the third part for another. The two parts are amazingly intertwined. It is not only the shipwreck that creates a link between these two layers, but also the themes that are introduced in Pi's childhood and rise again during his survival. This way the third part is an inseparable layer of the second, bringing just an extra spics to it.

Diagram 4: Second part's plot diagram

3. *The first part*

Now that the plots of the third and second part are established, explained and sketched, it is easy to determine the plot of the first part and the novel. The first part starts with the “Author’s note” serving as an introduction to the story that follows. It lays the ground for the upcoming setting, themes, motifs as well as imagery and symbols.

The voice that answered had an Indian lilt to its Canadian accent, light but unmistakable, like a trace of incense in the air. “That was a very long time ago”, he said. Yet he agreed to meet. We met many times. He showed me the yellowed newspaper clippings that made him briefly, obscurely famous. He told me his story. All the while I took notes. Nearly a year later, after considerable difficulties, I received a tape and a report from the Japanese Ministry of Transport. (Martel 2012, XV)

After the introduction made by the Author, the rising action – Pi’s childhood – follows. In this scenario, Pi’s childhood acts as a rising action. The shipwreck still acts as a twist and an introduction to the new rising action – Pi’s survival – followed by the climax and sudden falling action.

Diagram 5: First part's plot diagram

Each part acts as a layer of the story that only when combined with other layers makes the story whole. The third part is the juicy core, the second part is the white part of an orange, and the first part protects them both with its shiny orange peel. Together they create the first class tasty orange which will quench your thirst for exotic things.

Starting with the simplified version of traditional plot diagram, moving along the plots of the third and second part and finally reaching the *Life of Pi* plot diagram, different versions of triangle are presented. Each part, as well as the whole novel, has the shape of the traditional plot diagram. It may look a bit rough on the edges with small digressions from the main path, but in the end the plot has the shape of the traditional novel.

It starts with an introduction that states the thesis of the story – “a story that will make you believe in God” (Martel 2012, XIII). The rising action with its many digressions follows, leading us to the climax of the story – Pi is saved after remarkable, unbelievable journey. If that is not enough for us to believe in the existence of God, the falling action and untypical denouement make the point yet again using different words. Therefore, the plot of *Life of Pi* has a shape of a traditional novel.

Diagram 6: *Life of Pi* plot diagram

However, the many digressions, the untypical denouement that does not really give clarification but opens new questions, the untypical introduction and the Author's intrusions throughout the story, as well as the language, style and choice of three different narrators, make this novel contemporary novel rather than a traditional one.

Symbolism

Structure, language, style, tone and plot are all crucial steps in creating a novel. Structure is an empty shell that needs to be filled up with the correct language that creates a specific style and gives recognizable tone to the novel, while the plot combines it all to help bring home the main idea of the novel. In order to express the idea as vividly and beautifully as possible, it is necessary to dive into the waters of symbolism.

Life of Pi is full of different symbols and metaphors constantly pointing to the main idea. It seems that the strongest ones have to do with names. In everyday life names carry strong meanings. On a certain level the name we carry determines us, creates us, and becomes us, so it is not strange that in a novel name would carry a specific role and meaning.

The first and the biggest name in the novel is Pi. The name itself is actually not a name at all but a shortening of Pi's true name – Piscine Molitor. Piscine Molitor is a name given to a boy as an odd honour to a Paris swimming pool.

But no swimming pool in Mamaji's eyes matched the glory of the Piscine Molitor. It was the crowning aquatic glory of Paris, indeed, of the entire civilized world.

It was a pool the gods would have delighted to swim in. Molitor had the best competitive swimming club in Paris. (Martel 2012, 14)

The boy's full name is Piscine Molitor Patel, but he changes it to something simpler and less degrading after being called "Pissing Patel" in school. It is not only that his name meant a specific pool, but its pronunciation sounded as a basic human need – pissing. This is why the boy changed his name to Pi. It is short of Piscine, but it also has a powerful meaning.

I got up from my desk and hurried to the blackboard. Before the teacher could say a word, I picked up a piece of chalk and said as I wrote:

*My name is
Piscine Molitor Patel.
Known to all as*

– I double underlined the first two letters of my given name –

Pi Patel

For good measure I added

$\pi = 3.14$

and I drew a large circle, which I then sliced in two with a diameter, to evoke the basic lesson of geometry. (Martel 2012, 29-30)

Pi is an irrational number with no end. It is known as a transcendental number. In changing his name to the simplest possible version that does not sound odd when pronounced, Pi did not only change his name and stopped the laughing party, he named himself after one thing that goes far beyond basic human needs and objects. The one thing that fascinates both ordinary people as well as scientists. Therefore, the name Pi stands as a symbol of transcendental infinitive greatness that is an unavoidable part of everything and everyone.

The second name that carries specific meaning is the name of a tiger. His true name, just like Pi's, is not Richard Parker. Or better to say, it was not originally Richard Parker. Richard Parker was actually the name of the man who found the tiger, but somehow tiger's name, Thirsty, and man's name got mixed up in the papers received

by the zoo and the tiger got stuck with Richard Parker instead of Thirsty. Richard Parker's original name means nothing special. It was given to him because he was found near the water. Meanwhile, his new name carries a certain weight. Having a human name makes him special in a way that Pi perceives him differently than he does other animals. He is far more inclined to anthropomorphise the tiger than any other animal. The name Richard Parker stands as a symbol of a thin line between animal and human.

The third and final name is Mr. Satish Kumar. There are two Mr. Kumars in the novel. One is Pi's biology teacher at Petit Séminaire and the other is Pi's Muslim mentor. Interesting is that the two men carry the same name and have the same importance in Pi's life, but their beliefs are of the opposite ends. One is an atheist that thrusts only the facts of science, while other is a devoted Muslim who believes in God. It seems that the reason why these two carry the same name is to show that there are always two sides to the same coin.

I'll be honest about it. It is not atheists who get stuck in my craw, but agnostics. Doubt is useful for a while. We must all pass through the garden of Gethsemane. If Christ played with doubt, so must we. If Christ spent an anguished night in a prayer, if He burst out from the Cross, "My God, my God, why have you forsaken me?" then surely we are also permitted doubt. But we must move on. To choose doubt as a philosophy of life is akin to choosing immobility as means of transportation. (Martel 2012, 37-38)

Facts and scientific reality and spiritual faith are seemingly incompatible but both are just one's way of perceiving and dealing with the world. Therefore, the name Mr. Satish Kumar stands as a symbol of simultaneous, opposite and multiple viewpoints that do not have to mutually exclude one another.

The structure promised an interesting story and the language, style and tone helped to create a marvellous contemporary plot which is further spiced up with a daring use of name symbolism. What is more, this symbolism does not only give a life to technical parts of the novel, it also brings the reader one step closer to the underlying themes of the novel and the main idea.

Themes

The novel is full of different themes. Some are more and some less important. Luckily, in the vast scope of themes three persistently stand out –anthropomorphism, religion and science, and self-perception. What is more, they are natural extension and combination of previously mentioned symbolisms.

1. Anthropomorphism

Anthropomorphism is also called personification and it is attribution of human characteristics to non-human beings or things. Its history as a part of human history dates far back, 40,000 years ago. It is not strange that something that has been a part of human life for so long would find its way to literature.

In *Life of Pi* anthropomorphism is one of the crucial themes. The first indicator of it is that the main character lives in a zoo and has a father who lectures him about true animal and human nature.

There are animals we haven't stopped by. Don't think they're harmless. Life will defend itself no matter how small it is. Every animal is ferocious and dangerous. It may not kill you, but it will certainly injure you. It will scratch you and bite you, and you can look forward to a swollen, pus-filled infection, as high fever and ten-day stay in the hospital. (Martel 2012, 50)

He would do anything; even make Pi watch a tiger kill a goat, to make him stop seeing animals as equals.

With sudden ease the trapdoor slid open. Silence fell again, except for bleating and the *click-click* of the goat's hooves against the floor.

A streak of black and orange flowed from one cage to the next.

Normally the big cats were not given food one day a week, to simulate conditions in the wild. We found out later that Father had ordered that Mahisha not be fed for three days.

I don't know if I saw blood before turning into Mother's arms or if I daubed it on later, in my memory, with a big brush. But I heard. It was enough to scare the living vegetarian daylights out of me. (Martel 2012, 47)

It is not that the father believes humans are superior; it is just that he believes that getting too comfortable with animals and projecting your own thoughts and actions onto them can lead to catastrophe for both sides. In the end, he believes humans to be the worst kind of the animal.

Just beyond the ticket booth Father had had painted on a wall in bright red letters the question: DO YOU KNOW WHICH IS THE MOST DANGEROUS ANIMAL IN THE ZOO? An arrow pointed to a small curtain. There were so many eager, curious hands that pulled at the curtain that we had to replace it regularly. Behind it was a mirror. (Martel 2012, 40-41)

Father's good intentions, however, do not work out. Pi is still amazed with the tiger, and tiger having a human name – Richard Parker – does not help. It is easy to attribute human characteristics to a captured animal, and animal having a human name makes it so much harder to resist the temptation. Calling someone Richard Parker calls for completeness of a person and it is hard to imagine otherwise. Therefore, it is not strange that Pi, when left almost completely alone, except for a tiger, cannot but anthropomorphise the tiger. The only way to survive is to make him equal and important.

The theme of anthropomorphism is a strong repeating theme in the novel, but also in everyday life. Luckily for Pi, treating Richard Parker this way did not cost him his life, as it could have, but it did cost him his beliefs. Ever since Richard Parker came to the zoo, Pi had had a special relationship with him, or at least he thought so. Later on the boat the relationship deepened and deepened until it was completely shattered on the Mexican coast. It fell to non-existent the moment they got saved and Richard Parker just walked away. Pi's father tried to warn him about this and many other disappointments that rise from anthropomorphising an animal, but Pi did not listen.

The detailed process resulting in an abrupt end does not only show how anthropomorphism takes place, but also shows that there are two natures which can never be unified – human and animal nature. It also shows that it is important to see things clearly and call them what they truly are, without adding ornaments.

2. Religion and science

Another important theme that stretches through the novel is religion and science. Pi grows up in a family that deals with animals and is fairly educated about animal nature. He himself explores and investigates around the zoo and has a special bond with his science teacher Mr. Kumar, deepening his knowledge of things.

To his ears, when animal felt the urge to mate, it said “Gregor Mendel”, recalling the father of genetics, and when it was time to show it mettle, “Charles Darwin”, the father of natural selection, and what we took to be bleating, howling, chirping and screeching were but the thick accents of foreigners. When Mr. Kumar visited the zoo, it was to take the pulse of the universe, and his stethoscopic mind always confirmed to him that everything way in order, that everything was order. (Martel 2012, 34)

After all, his nick name has a scientific origin meaning nothing more than the irrational number. It suffices to say that science is an important part of Pi’s life and an important theme of the novel.

However, Pi, owing it to his mother, is also interested in spirituality. He explores three big religions – Hinduism, Christianity and Islam. He finds the study of religion as important as the study of science and becomes a devoted follower of all three religions throughout his life: “Bapu Gandhi said, ‘All religions are true’ I just want to love God,” I blurted out, and looked down, red in the face (Martel 2012, 92).

Pi’s knowledge of scientific things helps him a lot on the open sea, especially the knowledge of animals and animal nature. Religion, however, is still the number one place he goes to when feeling low on morale. No matter how far away from civilization and how low on everything, he thrusts his last breath to spirituality and science.

The differences between two are as obvious as the sun in the sky but similarities are harder to see. Pi sees them and makes them visible on each step, but the most obvious scene is the meeting of two Mr. Kumars. They are two sides of the same coin, as religion and science are. The recurring theme of both religion and science does not only point out their importance, strength and weaknesses, but it shows the necessity for the two to work together or at least side by side without diminishing each other’s worth. If Mr. Kumars can feed a zebra together, so can religion and science.

Mr. Kumar went first, dipping his hand over the fence. The zebra's thick, strong, black lips grasped the carrot eagerly. Mr. Kumar wouldn't let go. The zebra sank its teeth into the carrot and snapped it in two. It crunched loudly on the treat for a few seconds, then reached for the remaining piece, lips flowing over Mr. Kumar's fingertips. He released the carrot and touched the zebra's soft nose.

It was Mr. Kumar's turn. He wasn't so demanding of the zebra. Once it had his half of the carrot between its lips, he let go. The lips hurriedly moved the carrot into the mouth.

Mr. and Mr. Kumar looked delighted.

"A zebra, you say?" said Mr. Kumar.

"That's right," I replied. "It belongs to the same family as the ass and the horse."

"The Rolls-Royce of equids," said Mr. Kumar.

"What a wondrous creature," said Mr. Kumar.

"This one's Grant's zebra," I said.

Mr. Kumar said, "*Equus burchelli boehmi*."

Mr. Kumar said, "*Allahu akbar*."

I said, "It's very pretty."

We looked on. (Martel 2012, 111-12)

Approaches may be different, but they lead to the same thing. In Pi's case it was the survival.

3. Self-perception

The third theme of the novel is self-perception. It is probably the most important theme since it combines the previous two. Pi's perception of himself is related to all most important things in his life – the zoo, animals, Richard Parker, science and religion.

The first thing he came to know in life was the life in the zoo. He played around animals all the time and came to know their nature by heart. In a way, part of his personality was formed under the influence of animals.

To me, it was paradise on earth. I have nothing but the fondest memories of growing up in the zoo. I lived the life of a prince. What maharaja's son had such vast, luxuriant grounds to play about? What palace had such a masterpiece? My alarm clock during my childhood was a pride of lions. They

were no Swiss clocks, but the lions could be counted upon to roar their heads off between five-thirty and six every morning. Breakfast was punctuated by the shrieks and cries of howler monkeys, hill mynahs and Moluccan cockatoos. (Martel 2012, 17-18)

Later he established a close relationship with different religions. The first was Hinduism, which was a part of his life from the very birth. Then it was Christianity, and finally Islam. Each contributed to shaping a young man's personality and added another layer onto previously established personality under the influence of zoo animals.

At the same time as Pi explored religions, he also deepened his knowledge of science. This knowledge polished the part of personality created under the influence of zoo animals, but it also overlapped by the layer of personality formed under the influence of spirituality. The science and religion overlap and create a unified layer in Pi's personality.

These layers and their mixture are important later in Pi's life, especially when he finds himself lost not only on the open sea, but also lost to the world and himself. The horror of shipwreck and survival took its toll on the young Pi and he was left to re-evaluate his perception of who he is. Some parts of him seemed forever lost, but he, his persona, managed to survive thanks to the presence of Richard Parker. Richard Parker stood for all the zoo animals Pi grew up with – the very first layer of Pi's personality. The need to tame the tiger stood for the scientific knowledge Pi had – the second layer of Pi's personality, which was, yet again, interlaced by Pi's need for deeper explanation of things that stood for Pi's interest in religions and spirituality – the third layer of Pi's personality.

The theme of self-perception occurred throughout the novel dressed in different gowns, depending on the need of the story. Regardless of its appearance and changeability, the self-perception theme is a very strong theme of the novel, especially since the novel could be viewed as a Bildungsroman. By telling his story Pi did not only tell a story of a great shipwreck and even greater survival. He told a story of a young man's growth, his ups and downs and his perception of himself. He pointed out that the way we perceive ourselves, be it through religion or science or animals, is in the end the most important thing. According to our self-perception we create our life.

By analysing the themes of the novel the analysis of the novel itself is complete, or at least the formalist analysis. Different formal elements work together to create the novel. They make the perfect synthesis that delivers the complete product. If one element were missing the product would be incomplete.

The structure is the least creative, but the most important element – it sets the ground for the story. This empty bowl is then filled up with different words in different relations to each other, creating a specific language, style and tone by which **A** novel is recognized and separated from other works of art. With its specific plot the novel sets on an even more fulfilling journey of diversity by adding unique symbolisms that lead to the theme of the novel. Formalists were right when they stressed the importance of formal elements of the work. They do create the core of the work and without analysing them no work could be truly understood.

However, although analysing the elements of the work is important and fruitful, it does not say enough about the work. It seems that it only scratches the surface of the work, leaving the juiciest parts forever lost in time and space. To truly grasp the meaning and importance of some art, further analysis is needed. Since the formal elements were already covered and discovered, it is only natural to dive into the pool of interpretation.

At this point I feel the need to recall the chapter on literary theory, especially the explanation of different literary schools. Four schools were mentioned – formalism, structuralism, post-structuralism and reader response theory.

So far the approach of formalism was used to analyse the novel, and it led us to the point that demands further analysis. Since formalism is predecessor of structuralism, structuralism would not be a suitable choice for further analysis. It is unlikely it would lead much further.

Luckily, post-structuralism stands as an opposition to structuralism and it might lead to new discoveries. Post-structuralism has many different approaches, such as response theory – the next approach to analysing *Life of Pi*. Since reader response theory focuses on the reader and his experience of a literary work, it is necessary to point out that the interpretation that follows is my interpretation of the work according to my interpretive community and “I say it (we know) to you now, knowing full that you will agree with me (that is, understand) only if you already agree with me” (Fish 1980, 173).

3.3. *Life of Pi* – analysis part 2

The interpretation of *Life of Pi* starts at the point where analysis ended – themes. The three most important themes are anthropomorphism; religion and science, and self-perception. Self-perception is the theme that combines the previous two and is, therefore, the most important for the interpretation.

For interpretation to be full and detailed, the background on which the interpretation of *Life of Pi* lays has to be laid out and explained first. Since the most important theme is self-perception it is crucial to recall some of the best thinkers of our civilization and their concepts of being. In order to be able to perceive oneself, one first has to exist.

Philosophical background

The famous quote “I think, therefore I am” written by the French philosopher René Descartes in his work *Meditations on First Philosophy* does not only prove that if one thinks one must certainly exist, but it is based on an interesting theory of categories of being. The theory that reaches far back even before Descartes’ time and had a strong impact on the way society today perceives the world – dualism. Yann Martel himself might have based his novel on this theory either intentionally or unintentionally. The theory is irretrievably interlaced with our society and history

In both cases we look at an animal and see a mirror. The obsession with putting ourselves at the centre of everything is the bane not only of theologians but also of zoologists. (Martel 2012, 41)

1. Dualism

Dualism is the position that advocates the dual existence of man. Mind and body are two separate parts of man and they are by no means identical. Body and mind are two fundamentally different components.

Descartes

Dualism has existed for ages, or at least as far back as Plato and Aristotle go. In their work both Aristotle and Plato stated that human mind and soul cannot be identified with physical body. Descartes later reinforced this concept of dualism known today under the name of Cartesian dualism. In a way his line of thinking was nothing new, but his mechanical view of the world in which animals are nothing more than a mere body without a soul that follows its instincts and laws of nature, while humans consist of both body and mind and are therefore higher on the hierarchy tree is still very influential and present in today's society.

Aristotle

For Descartes animals are without a soul and, therefore, unimportant, but how does Aristotle categorise different entities? In his work *On the Soul* Aristotle focuses on the nature of living things and their different operations. According to Aristotle, plants have only a nutritive soul of growth and metabolism – the minimum for any living being. Animals, on the other hand, have this minimum plus perceptive soul of pain, pleasure and desire but they lack the third and the most important – the faculty of reason. It is this that distinguishes humans from other animals – intellect.

What is more, in his work *Nicomachean Ethics*, Aristotle addresses the question of three bad states of character or three sources of wrongdoing: vice, incontinence and brutishness. The opposite of vice is virtue and the opposite of incontinence is continence, but when it comes to brutishness it is hard to define its opposite in the same manner in which vice's and incontinence's opposites are defined. It seems that the only possible opposite to brutishness would be a superhuman virtue, which is not the direct opposite, but the highest possible form of good. What is interesting here is not only that Aristotle finds it hard to define the direct opposite for brutishness, but the fact that neither brutishness nor its opposite are accessible to a human being. Virtue and continence, as well as vice and incontinence, are typically human (Šumič-Riha 2002, 8) and one has to strive to act in accordance with virtue and continence rather than vice and incontinence. However, when brutishness and superhuman virtue are in question, one is not expected to strive to act in accordance with superhuman virtue to avoid brutishness, since both brutishness and superhuman virtue are something

inaccessible to a human being. (Šumič-Riha 2002, 8) They are two extremes that fall out of human nature. In other words, one should stick to one's own nature and leave the extremes to be inaccessible extremes.

2. Dualism and the modern world

Aristotle's view on dualism is fairly simple and straightforward but it seems that it is in human nature to go for the extremes. Throughout human history many have tried to reach superhuman virtue by different means, and many have explored how deep brutishness goes. However, in order to set on the exploration of the extremes one has to accept the concept of dualism shown either by Descartes or Aristotle.

Dualism seems to be the leading concept even today. We perceive both body and thoughts; it is only the way we explain their relation to each other that differs. Nonetheless, the division into the two remains. This concept goes deep into the roots of both science and religion.

Theory of evolution

Aristotle's hierarchy of souls seems to take a new direction because of the theory of evolution. According to the theory, plants appear slightly earlier on the evolutionary tree, than animals and finally humans – the highest developed form of animals known so far. There is, however, one difference which explains the need of some to fall into exploration of brutishness – humans are animals even though the language and our possibility of civilization distinguish us from other animals. For those who strongly believe in evolution as such, humans are animals in their nature and will always remain animal nature; therefore, brutishness is a part of us as well and there is no shame in exploring it and embracing it.

Not many think this way, or at least not many are inclined to say it so firmly since, in their eyes, acknowledging it diminishes human value. Old belief in dualism that places humans high above animals is deeply rooted in society. It is because of this way many still see humans as superior to animals and think of animals as less important, if not as unimportant. It is at this point that many problems emerge and

why so many activists as well as artists fight for animal rights and reestablishment of animal position in the world.

Anthropomorphism

We already saw in the chapter on Canadian literature what some solutions by some Canadian writers are when it comes to the question of the position of animals in society. What strikes me as interesting is the growing tendency to not only see animals as equals but to see them as our other selves. This tendency to depict animals as humans, as human alter ego has been present in human history for a long, long time, even before the questions of animal rights became popular. It is more commonly known as anthropomorphism. By attributing animals with human attributes we do not only reject Descartes believe that animals do not have souls, but we also reject our superiority and acknowledge the animal in us.

According to the French philosopher Jean-Paul Sartre, the self exists only in relation to others, thus our human self exists only in relation to the animal self. We define our self, our being according to animals, but we also define the self of animals, their being according to us. Such reasoning is circular and calls for a new way of reasoning, a new way of defining our human self.

3. The limit between animal and human

The distinction between animal and human self has been a growing subject of many contemporary philosophers as well, such as the German philosopher Helmuth Plessner, the Italian philosopher Giorgio Agamben and the French philosopher Jacques Derrida.

Agamben

In his work *The Open. Man and Animal*, Agamben rethinks a classic topos of Western metaphysics – the relationship between man and animal. He rejects any kind of censorship regarding the question of the relationship between man and animal, because he thinks that censorship does no good. Censorship will actually do

more harm and produce irreducible indistinctness between man and animal. The solution for Agamben lies in overcoming the anthropological machine. The anthropological machine “is a description of the dichotomy between man and animals in the form of a working entity, the machine” (Thrown into the World 2013). Agamben even states that there are two types of anthropological machine, one being modern and the other pre-modern. Modern one creates non-human by zoomorphising human and pre-modern creates non-human by anthropomorphising animal. (Agamben 2001, 113) In the end, both are unacceptable to Agamben and he finds that only overcoming the anthropological machine will stop circular reasoning and free man and animal of mutual captivity. (Agamben 2001, 114) By disabling the differentiation between animal and man, man is saved from the dichotomy between animal and human as well as from the dichotomy between heavenly and earthly nature.

Derrida

On the other hand, Derrida, in his *The Animal That Therefore I Am*, does not go into specific details about the distinction between man and human, but he does address the problem. He asks himself who he is after he is seen naked by his cat. To him the cat is not inferior but is animal-other with its own point of view. In his own way he breaks with Aristotelian tradition of animal by rethinking the limit between animal and man and suggesting that new words should be used when addressing this problem. Just like Agamben, Derrida does not find a solution in deleting lines between man and animal, as many other activist do. He sees the solution in multiplying them, making limitrophy his subject. In a way, Derrida protects animal-others from anthropocentric homogeneity, but also from the reduction to Descartes’ “animal machine” (Buns 2008, 416).

Plessner

Plessner’s work he does not deal so much with how to solve the problem of the limit between man and animal, as he actually defines levels of the organic and speaks of human dichotomy between heavenly and earthly nature. His stand is somewhat in conflict with Agamben’s and Derrida’s stand, but it came first and lies on Plessner’s

innovative principles of philosophical anthropology – “the study of the nature of individuals through their experiences” (Britannica 2015).

In his theory of existence he differentiated humans from animals. To him plants have utterly open self-expression and they have no ability to express their preferences regarding their environment. Animals, however, know their own borders and are pressed back within them, thus constantly limiting their expression. Finally, humans alternate between open and closed intentionality. We have these borders and we are these borders. “When individuals transcend their outer self and realize their inner life, he believed, they are open to perceptions, experiences, and expressions that have a greater sociological and historical significance” (Britannica 2015).

4. Question of man

Plessner’s theory of existence and his whole philosophical anthropology lies on a specific socio-politic ground of 1920s. Both Plessner’s and Max Scheler’s philosophical anthropology was created as an expression of the crisis of the bourgeois world, its culture and philosophy. (Plessner 1981, 441) However, what is interesting is that Plessner breaks with the Platonic-Christian tradition as well as with Cartesian tradition of understanding of the world and man.

It seems that Plessner’s philosophical anthropology was created at the very beginning of breaking with classic philosophical theories, but also the very beginning of efforts to bridge the institutionalised gap between science and philosophy. This is why Plessner started with rethinking philosophical past, scientific past as well as human past. Plessner lived in a highly scientific-oriented and material society so it is not strange he took this hard task upon himself.

The problem itself is still relevant even today, as we saw in Agamben’s rethinking of limits between man and animal. However, at the root of the controversy between humanities and science lies more relevant question and that is the question of man. Who is he? How can his being be defined? As we saw, this is an old question that exists from the beginning of our time. Philosophy tried to answer the question as well as religion did and later science, but it seems that every philosopher, every religion and every scientific theory has its own answer to it.

Each historical period adds a new point of view on the topic of the question of man, just as it does with art. If both art and the question of man are tackled ever differently depending on the historical era, it would make for an interesting reading to see how art itself tackles the question of man. Or at least the work in question.

Interpretation

To start off with the interpretation of *Life of Pi* based on written backgrounds, I find it necessary to first point out the genre this book belongs to and only then proceed to other subsections of interpretation. Many see *Life of Pi* as Bildungsroman or an adventure story, but for me this novel is a modern fable-like allegory which acts as a perfect criticism of the modern world.

1. Modern fable-like allegory

One may ask why fable-like allegory. How do the two go together? I have already shown how fables changed throughout the history of literature and that in modern world fables take on a fairly different structure than they did at the beginning. Therefore, it is not strange to have a fable-like story which does not feature only animals, but also humans, as *Life of Pi* does. Furthermore, fables have always been a perfect genre for a literary device known as allegory. Their simple and traditional structure is a perfect ground for conveying deeper, hidden meanings through different symbolism resulting in political, moral or spiritual critique. In Yann Martel words:

The use of animal in his novel, he explained, was for reasons of craft rather than of sentiment. Speaking before his tribe, naked, he was only human and therefore possibly-likely-surely-a liar. But dressed in furs and feathers, he became a shaman and spoke a greater truth. (Martel 2010, 29)

Considering Yann Martel's own words, the history of fable and its relation to allegory, the importance and history of animals in Canadian literature, and formalist analysis of *Life of Pi* there is really no other way than to see the novel as a modern fable-like allegory. Fable-like since its structure, language, style and plot are almost typically

traditional. Allegory since its symbolism and themes speak of greater issues than a mere adventure and survival, and modern because of the combination of traditional literary devices with untypical characters of fables and specific contemporary symbolism and themes.

2. Dualism, the theory of evolution and religion

Now that the book is defined as a modern fable-like allegory, let's dive into the dark waters of interpretation. The three most important themes of the novel were seen, and philosophical background of such themes was explored, but it remains to investigate the connection between these philosophical issues and *Life of Pi*.

Both dualism and the theory of evolution have a special place in *Life of Pi*. The distinction between mind and body is present throughout the novel mainly as a basis for the evolutionary approach to the division between man and animal, but also as a basis of each presented religion. The criticism of dualism is therefore never direct, but conveyed through the criticism of the traditional division on man and animal, the criticism of anthropomorphism and, finally, the criticism of the distinction between scientific and religious self-perception.

Human superiority

Let me start with the traditional division on man and animal. The novel shows a great understanding of the theory of evolution and the hierarchy presented through it. It is this knowledge that allows for the criticism of traditional superiority of man and inferiority of animals.

Pi's father knows very well the nature of each and every animal in his zoo:

We came to the guinea pigs, the only other animals besides Mahisha to have been starved at Father's orders, having been denied their previous evening's meal. Father unlocked the cage. He brought out a bag of feed from his pocket and emptied it on the floor.

"You see these guinea pigs?"

"Yes, Father."

The creatures were trembling with weakness as they frantically nibbled their kernels of corn.

“Well...” He leaned down and scooped one up.

“They’re not dangerous.” The other guinea pigs scattered instantly. (Martel 2012, 50),

but he also knows the extent of human nature. Unlike most visitors and people around him, he treats animals with respect acknowledging their nature as their deserved right and nothing out of the ordinary. This is partly because of his knowledge of the theory of evolution and partly because of the fact that animal-others, if we borrow the term from Derrida, are our fellow animals, neither superior nor inferior to us. The other reason why he acknowledges the animal-others as he does is because of the fact that he does not look the other way when it comes to human nature. He knows that we are also animals and that we are capable of great brutishness. What is more, Pi’s father does not only acknowledge animal-others nature and sees human nature as it is, he is also aware of the fact that most people do not see this as such and that because of this denial of our nature, we are the most dangerous animal of all.

We commonly say in the trade that the most dangerous animal in a zoo is Man. In a general way we mean how our species’ excessive predatoriness has made the entire planet our prey. (Martel 2012, 38)

By acknowledging animal-others’ nature and respecting it for what it is, and by stating the obvious yet neglected fact about deepness of human brutishness, Pi’s father went against the traditional superior position of man.

Self-perception and anthropomorphism

Another strong criticism in the novel is the criticism of anthropomorphism. As we saw before, anthropomorphism serves as a special way of defining our human self. However, we also saw that this kind of reasoning leads to circular reasoning with no end and it also diminishes the importance and value of animals and their nature.

Pi’s father conveys the same criticism of anthropomorphism and warns Pi about the possible danger of approaching animals in such a manner. Although he speaks

openly about human brutishness, he also speaks and respects animal brutishness. His stance is that animal is animal and will always act according to its nature, and we would be fools to think otherwise. Forgetting animal's real nature and attributing it with a human one is dangerous both for us and the animal, especially because we are attributing it with a human nature we ourselves are incapable of accepting for what it truly is.

Self-perception and religion

In the novel the opposition to defining our human self through anthropomorphism is presented. The opposition is religion, or generally speaking, spirituality. The question is how spirituality helps us define our human self.

Pi's investigations of three different religions and his ever growing love for any kind of spirituality gives us a fair inside into another machine of self-perception. The theory of evolution is one machine and spirituality is another. Through spirituality Pi discovers the human possibility for greatness and love. Spirituality teaches us to strive for the best. To strive to live according to, as Aristotle would put it, superhuman virtue rather than brutishness. It shows us the side of us we humans were always too afraid to explore because of its greatness.

Many thinkers would discard this way of thinking about human self as overly traditional and outdated, but the novel speaks of both the religious, traditional concept of man, and modern, scientific concept of man. By doing so, it does not only teach about two different approaches to it, but builds a basis for the criticism of the distinction between science and religion.

Self-perception and the combination of science and religion

In dual self-perception lies the answer to the ever growing gap between science and religion. *Life of Pi* teaches us that there are two ways of defining our human self, and each has its pros and cons. That is why some middle ground between the two is necessary, according to *Life of Pi*. If we truly want to perceive our human self to its true extent, then we must accept both approaches.

Science teaches us about our body, how it came to be, what it is capable of and how it affects our behaviour. On the other hand, religion teaches us about greatness and how we should always strive for it. The two seem irreconcilable, but Pi takes both and combines them into his unique perception of his human self. Being strongly grounded and acknowledging the wide span of human nature, but at the same time seeing that there is more to it than pure genes and animal instincts, is what frees us and gives us long lost freedom of open life.

3. Science vs. religion

The criticism of dualism through the criticism of the traditional division on man and animal, the criticism of anthropomorphism and, finally, the criticism of the distinction between scientific and religious self-perception, led to the conclusion about true position of man and his human self. It is the position that lies somewhere halfway between scientific and religious approach to self-perception.

However, this position is the position that Plessner finds problematic. According to him, this middle position is the position that leaves a man without a home, or differently said; man is forever lost between two worlds. His self is elusive to him. The position is problematic to Plessner since, according to him, man is trapped between two worlds and is unable to go either way, but if we look at it as Pi does, it is not problematic at all. To Pi we are not trapped between two worlds. The worlds are part of us, both of them. The position is not so much between the two worlds as it is the point in which the two worlds collide – the contact point.

Through such a view on self-perception, the criticism of today's distinction between science and religion is created. We live in a society that reached the peak of industrialism and materialism long ago and which still hangs on it although both industrialism and materialism are far gone. Science did take us far and showed us how many things work. It helped us create many useful things that allow us to live more freely and easily. It got to the bottom of how nature works. It explained how we were created and it strives to explain ever more, for example, how we react in a certain way and how we perceive things as we do. The only problem is that no matter how innovative its approaches and results are, it seems to lack a certain deeper understanding. It is no longer enough to know that music written in mol rather than

dur triggers different parts of our brain. We strive to know why it is so. Why this exact part of the brain? This is the point at which science fails to offer any explanation but we still strive for it just like we strive to know more about our self, beyond mere biological and neurobiological processes.

Many philosophers see the answer to this in combining philosophy and science. In applying a philosophical approach where the scientific one reaches the dead end. This way of thinking can be extended to the humanities in general – to reconcile long growing gap between sciences and humanities in order to get fuller understanding of the world around us and our self. Therefore, it is not strange that Pi advocates the reconciliation of science and religion.

Yann Martel said, when asked about his intentions of writing the story, that reality is not only one, and that according to this there are also different interpretations of reality, or as Pi puts it:

The world isn't just the way it is. It is how we understand it, no? And in understanding something, we bring something to it, no? (Martel 2012, 405)

Science is one interpretation of reality, philosophy another and religion the third. And these are not only interpretations of reality; they are also interpretations of our self.

If we want to break the anthropological machine as Agamben stated, we first have to reconcile different interpretations of our self. Only by doing that will we get a chance to define our self. This is what *Life of Pi* teaches us through its rehabilitation of spirituality in connection to science. To get to the next level of knowledge and understanding we must first break with the traditional divisions on all possible levels.

Conclusion

The thesis acted as an introduction to the specific relationship that exists between society and art, especially literature; it studied and pointed out the progress of literature and its counterpart literary theory throughout their and human history; it introduced literary tools used for analysis of *Life of Pi* by introducing and analysing two different yet similar examples – *Animal Farm* and *Tainaron*; it made a connection between chosen examples and *Life of Pi* through study of fables and role of animals in Canadian literature; it analysed *Life of Pi* by purely formalist approach; it revealed the main themes of the book through formalist analysis; it set philosophical ground for further interpretation of main themes; it analysed the main themes based on the previously established philosophical ground and their relation to fables and animals in Canadian literature, and finally, it interpreted *Life of Pi* as a modern fable-like allegory, a criticism of modern society.

The importance of art, not only as a medium that follows and reflects society's progress, but also as a medium that serves as one of society's greatest criticism teaching us about our wrongs and our rights is shown. The role of art may seem simple and unimportant, but art is everywhere. It follows us through our lives; documents our lives and makes them complete. It is the number one medium of escape and number one medium of harsh criticism. Art teaches us what is wrong and what is right. It points out problems as soon as they arrive and it makes them visible to everyone. Most importantly, it defines our future and leads us to our next step as society. Art does not only follow, but also creates society as we know it.

The very relationship between society and art arrives from art's possibility to create. It is art, especially literature, that tells many stories about our history. Without the rise of literature we would not know anything about our ancestors, about how they lived, what were their preoccupations, what they thought, how they acted. It was literature's possibility to create something from merely observing society of its time that brought us the atmosphere and knowledge of that time. As it observed and documented certain period of history it also influenced and consequently changed society. This change in society was influenced by literature, but the change itself influenced and demanded the change in literature so that it can again document society and, especially, society's change.

Literary theory is an unavoidable product of cyclical changes in society and literature. As literature started to point out more and more things and society changed more and more rapidly, it was only a matter of time before the new change in society and literature would create a special device for monitoring, defining and studying literature itself. When it finally arrived, it developed literature even further, but the very core of it remained intact. Literature still changed with society and still contributed to society's change. The only difference is that now literary theory was there to document the changes in literature and consequently in society. By monitoring and analysing literature, literary theory contributed to the rapid change of literature which then contributed to the rapid change in society, starting a new cycle of a new kind of literature and a new kind of literary theory. The three influence each other and remain forever connected.

Since the three are inseparable it is only logical to use the newcomer to the trio to explain how a specific literary work was created, but also how it relates to society of its time. There are many different works and literary theory approaches available, almost as many as there are periods in history. However, one literary theory approach is enough to analyse one literary work. Formalist approach is the ideal literary approach to show the hidden *Animal Farm's* criticism of society. On the other hand, for *Tainaron*, the ideal literary approach that shows its criticism of society is the post-structuralist approach. In the end, both approaches lead to the same result – seeing the literary work in question as a document and criticism of its time. The literary works are different, the literary approaches that analyse them are different and so is society and the time they speak of, but basic technique and its result is the same regardless of the time, work or approach. Therefore, if the underlying technique is the same, why not take the approaches that were used in analysing *Animal Farm* and *Tainaron* to analyse *Life of Pi*? There is no need for any other literary approach, if both formalist and post-structuralist approaches led us to the same conclusion about two different yet, in the end, similar works of art.

For this kind of decision to make more sense and to make analysis of *Life of Pi* simpler, the connection between the above examples and *Life of Pi* is defined. No matter that all literature is a reflection of society and its remedy; there are still different kinds of reflections and remedies. Each work of art is a unique reflection and offers its own, unique remedy. However, there may be works that are similar to it, and it is this similarity that makes us look at those reflections in relation to each other. The

three, *Animal Farm*, *Tainaron* and *Life of Pi*, are similar kinds of reflections because all three have animals featuring as their main characters, or one of the main characters. The tradition of animals in literature is long, dating back to the beginnings of fable, and it prevailed until today in many different shapes and sizes. One such shape is the tradition and importance of animals in Canadian literature. Just like society, literature and literary theory, the tradition of animals in literature, specifically in Canadian literature, changes according to the historical period and shape of society. Animals are one of the most durable themes of both literature and society, and anthropomorphism is one of the longest standing literary device for creating an allegory resulting in criticism of society.

A purely formalist approach to analysing *Life of Pi* reveals the beauty of the language, structure, style, tone and plot, which led us to the specific symbolism and themes. By analysing the novel in such a way, the connection between each single literary element becomes obvious. Each literary element tells its own story. However, elements tell the story of the work they form only when they are analysed in relation to other elements of the story. Without the detailed, formalist analysis of literary elements that create the novel and their relation to each other, the novel's unique reflection of society would remain unknown. Literary theory approaches and their use are the first step in understanding literary work and society that created it. Consequently, literary theory approaches are the first step of society's change.

By using formalist approach to analyse *Life of Pi* its unique reflection of society is revealed, but the remedy remains unseen. Another literary approach is taken, one that served ideally in the case of *Tainaron*, to further polish *Life of Pi*'s reflection of society and to make its remedy seen. The literary approach able to do so is known by the name reader response theory and it bases its interpretation on the previously mentioned relation between the three examples, the themes revealed by formalist analysis, and the philosophical background that both creates and explains the main themes of the novel. Only the combination of two different literary theory approaches reveals the true nature of society's reflection in *Life of Pi*.

Life of Pi reflects a deeply lost society. The society that struggles to survive, to keep its head above the water at any cost; society that lost its purpose long time ago but instead of finding a new one, it just circles the old one keeping it artificially important and worthwhile. The society that keeps on craving for a long lost home and does

nothing but keeps on living on the old fame will eventually destroy itself. Stagnation has never done any good to anyone.

Luckily there is art, the one product of society that lives and strives for the change in it, because change in society brings new forms of expression that change and develop art even further. *Life of Pi* strives for the same. Its idea of remedy for stale and purposeless society is a sort of rehabilitation of spirituality. By this I do not mean the restoration of the old concept of spirituality and finding society's purpose in it, but more something like reconciling spiritual approach to society's purpose with still active, although rotting, scientific approach to society's purpose. The society can be saved and changed only by reconciling the scientific and spiritual approach and by combining their pros to create a new purpose, the purpose that will find its roots in both approaches.

The idea of combining two seemingly irreconcilable approaches could be used concerning literary theory and philosophy as well. This thesis, on a certain level, deals with literary theory and its irreconcilable approaches. Even through analysis of *Life of Pi* the need to combine two approaches is seen. Only one approach was not enough for full analysis of the work. Joined powers were needed. From older literary theory approach certain things that clearly worked for so long were taken, and they were just upgraded by a new literary theory approach in order to make the most out of the literary work. Neither one nor other approach was taken at wholesale. One would see the point of doing so when it comes to the older approach, since if there is a new one the old one clearly has something missing. However, why take only a part of the new, by analogy, better approach and not the whole? The answer to this question lies in the fact that both approaches are new and old at one point. The old approach was once new and the new one will become the new old one, and so on and on and on. To stop this never ending circle in which every new approach is doomed to become old at certain point, and in which not one of so many new approaches ever solved a problem it should have been able to solve, it is important to combine the old and the new. In the case of analysing *Life of Pi*, this way of reasoning certainly lead to the better and completer interpretation.

Life of Pi is interpreted by the combination of different approaches, and the novel itself advocates the combination of religion and science when it comes to defining society's purpose. If we extend this reasoning even further, onto philosophy and the question of man, it would be reasonable to advocate the combination of both

philosophical schools in order to fully cover the question of man. Analytical philosophers and continental philosophers should work together to resolve the endless question of man. By working together philosophers can solve the question of man sooner and they can re-establish philosophy's place in society by working side by side with scientists.

Povzetek

Magistrsko delo je uvod v specifičen odnos, ki obstaja med družbo in umetnostjo, posebej književnostjo; analizira in izpostavlja napredek književnosti in literarne teorije skozi njihovo kot tudi človeško zgodovino; uvaja literarna orodja za analizo *Pijevega življenja* skozi uvajanje in analizo dveh različnih, a obenem tudi podobnih primerov, tj. *Živalske farme* in *Tainarona*; vzpostavlja povezavo med izbranimi primeri in *Pijevim življenjem* skozi analizo basni in vloge živali v kanadski književnosti; analizira *Pijevo življenje* s pomočjo formalističnega pristopa; razkriva glavne teme romana skozi formalistično analizo; postavlja filozofske temelje za nadaljnjo interpretacijo glavnih tem; analizira glavne teme glede na prej vzpostavljene filozofske temelje in njihov odnos do basni in živali v kanadski književnosti in nazadnje tudi interpretira *Pijevo življenje* kot moderno basensko alegorijo – kritiko moderne družbe.

Pomen umetnosti ne le kot medija, ki spremlja in odraža napredek družbe, ampak tudi kot medija, ki služi kot ena izmed večjih kritik družbe, ki uči o naših krivicah in pravicah, je prikazan kot tak. Vloga umetnosti se morda sprva res zdi enostavna in nepomembna, a je umetnost vseprisotna. Spremlja nas skozi naša življenja; jih dokumentira in naredi popolna. Umetnost je primarni medij, ko gre za beg in ravno tako primarni medij, ko gre za strogo kritiko. Umetnost nas uči, kaj je prav in kaj narobe. Izpostavlja probleme takoj, ko se pojavijo in jih izpostavi vsem. Kar je najpomembnejše, definira našo prihodnost in nas vodi k našemu naslednjemu koraku kot družba. Umetnost ne sledi, ampak tudi ustvarja družbo, kot jo poznamo.

Sam odnos med družbo in umetnostjo izhaja prav iz zmožnosti umetnosti, da sama ustvarja. Umetnost, posebej književnost, je tista, ki pripoveduje zgodbe o naši preteklosti. Brez dviga književnosti ne bi vedeli ničesar o naših prednikih, o tem, kako so živeli, s čim so se ukvarjali, kaj so mislili, kako so se obnašali. Zmožnost književnosti, da nekaj ustvari iz tega, da enostavno opazuje družbo svojega časa, je tista, ki nam je prinesla atmosfero in znanje o določenem času. Z opazanjem in dokumentiranjem določenega obdobja zgodovine je književnost vplivala na družbo in jo spremenila. Ta sprememba v družbi je nastala pod vplivom književnosti, a sama sprememba je vplivala in terjala nadaljnjo spremembo v književnosti, le da bi spet dokumentirala družbo in, posebej, družbeno spremembo.

Literarna teorija je neizogibni produkt cikličnih sprememb v družbi in književnosti. S tem, da je književnost začela izpostavlјati vse več in več stvari in se je družba začela

spreminjati vse hitreje in hitreje, je bilo samo vprašanje časa, kdaj bo nova sprememba v družbi in književnosti ustvarila posebno orodje za spremljanje, definiranje in študiranje književnosti same. Ko je to končno bilo ustvarjeno, je razvilo književnost še dlje, čeprav je samo jedro književnosti ostalo enako. Književnost se je še vedno spreminjala poleg družbe in je še vedno prispevala k družbeni spremembi. Edina razlika je ta, da sedaj obstaja literarna teorija, ki je dokumentirala spremembe v književnosti in posledično družbe. S spremljanjem in analiziranjem književnosti je literarna teorija prispevala k hitri spremembi v književnosti, ki je sama prispevala k hitri spremembi v družbi in tako začela nov krog nove zvrsti književnosti in nove literarne teorije. Vse tri imajo medsebojen vpliv in so večno povezane.

Glede na to, da so družba, književnost in literarna teorija neločljive, je smiselno uporabiti najnovejši element v omenjenem trojčku, da razložimo način, kako je specifično literarno delo narejeno in kako se nanaša na družbo svojega časa. Obstaja ogromno različnih del in pristopov k literarni teoriji, skoraj toliko, kot je obdobje v zgodovini. Vendar je en sam pristop k literarni teoriji dovolj za analizo enega književnega dela. Formalistični pristop je idealen za prikaz skrite kritike družbe v *Živalski farmi*. Po drugi strani je idealen pristop za prikazati kritiko družbe, kakršna je prisotna v *Tainaronu*, post strukturalistični pristop. Na koncu oba pristopa pripeljeta do istega rezultata – specifičnega književnega dela, videnega kot dokument in kritika svojega časa. Književna dela so drugačna, kot so tudi literarni pristopi uporabljeni v analizi drugačni, in tudi družba ter čas, o katerih dela govorijo, a osnovna tehnika in rezultat sta enaka ne glede na čas, delo ali pristop. Če je torej osnovna tehnika enaka, zakaj ne bi uporabili pristopov, ki so uporabljeni pri analizi *Živalske farme* in *Tainarona* za analizo *Pijevega življenja*? Ni potrebe po tretjem pristopu k literarni teoriji, če nas je tako formalistični kot post strukturalistični pristop pripeljal do istega sklepa o dveh različnih, ampak na koncu podobnih umetniških delih.

Da bi taka odločitev imela več smisla in da bi analiza *Pijevega življenja* bila bolj enostavna, je povezava med zgoraj navedenimi primeri in *Pijevim življenjem* definirana. Čeprav je celotna književnost odraz družbe in obenem neke vrste zdravilo zanjo, obstajajo tudi druga, različna zdravila in odrazi družbe. Vsako umetniško delo je unikatno odraz in ponuja svoje unikatno zdravilo. Vendar obstajajo dela, ki so si med seboj podobna in prav ta podobnost je tisto, čemu drugačne odraze analiziramo glede na druge. Trojica *Živalska farma*, *Tainaron* in *Pijevo življenje* so podobni odrazi, ker pri vseh treh v vlogi glavnih likov nastopajo živali. Tradicija živali v književnosti je

stara, sega vse do začetkov basni, in je v različnih oblikah prevladala vse do danes. Ena teh oblik je tradicija in pomembnost živali v kanadski literaturi. Podobno kot družba, književnost in literarna teorija, se je tradicija živali v književnosti, specifično v kanadski književnosti, spreminjala glede na zgodovinsko obdobje in obliko družbe. Živali so ena od najbolj trpežnih tem tako v književnosti kot v družbi. Antropomorfizem je ena najstarejših literarnih tehnik za ustvarjanje alegorij, iz katerih izhaja kritika družbe.

Povsem formalističen pristop k analizi *Pijevega življenja* razkriva lepoto jezika, strukture, stila, tona in zgodbe, ki nas pripeljejo do specifičnih simbolov in tem. Analizirajoč roman na ta način, postane povezava med vsakim literarnim elementom očitna. Vsak literarni element ima svojo zgodbo. Vendar elementi govoriijo zgodbo dela, katerega del so, le takrat, ko so analizirani v povezavi z drugimi elementi. Brez podrobne formalistične analize literarnih elementov romana in njihovega medsebojnega odnosa bi unikatni odraz družbe v romanu ostal neopažen. Literarna teorija, njeni pristopi in uporaba le-teh so prvi koraki k razumevanju literarnega dela in družbe, katera ga je ustvarila. Posledično je moč trditi, da so literarna teorija in njeni pristopi prvi korak k družbeni spremembi.

Z uporabo formalističnega pristopa k analizi *Pijevega življenja* je odkrit unikatni odraz družbe v romanu, a je zdravilo ostalo nevidno. Drugi pristop, ki se je izkazal za idealnega v primeru *Tainarona*, je bil uporabljen z namenom dodatno kristalizirati odraz družbe na podlagi *Pijevega življenja* in obenem odkriti njegovo zdravilo. Pristop, ki to zmore, je znan pod nazivom »reader response theory« in bazira svojo interpretacijo na omenjenem odnosu med tremi primeri, temah, ki jih razkrije formalistična analiza, in filozofskem ozadju, ki tako ustvarja kot razlaga glavne teme romana. Zgolj kombinacija dveh različnih pristopov lahko razkrije pravo naravo družbenega odraza v *Pijevem življenju*.

Pijevo življenje odseva globoko izgubljeno družbo. Družbo, ki se bori za preživetje, ki se bori za ohranitev glave nad vodo za vsako ceno; družbo, ki je izgubila svoj namen dolgo nazaj in ki namesto, da najde nov namen, zgolj kroži okrog starega in ga umetno drži pokonci. Družba, ki hrepeni za dolgo izgubljenim domom in ne dela nič, poleg, da živi na stari slavi, se bo sčasoma uničila. Stagnacija nikoli nima pozitivnega vpliva.

Na srečo obstaja umetnost, produkt družbe, kateri živi in teži k spremembi v njej, saj sprememba v družbi pomeni spremembo in razvoj umetnosti same. *Pijevo življenje*

teži k istemu. Ideja romana kot zdravila za brezciljno in zastarelo družbo je vrsta rehabilitacije duhovnosti. S tem ni mišljena obnova starega koncepta duhovnosti in iskanja namena družbe v njem, temveč prej uskladitev duhovnega pristopa k namenu družbe s še vedno aktivnimi, četudi izkrivljenimi znanstvenimi pristopi k namenu družbe. Družbo je moč rešiti zgolj z uskladitvijo znanstvenega in duhovnega pristopa in kombiniranjem prednosti in slabosti le-teh, da bi ustvarili nov namen, namen, ki bo našel svoje začetke v obeh pristopih.

Ideja kombiniranja dveh navidezno nezdružljivih pristopov bi se lahko uporabila tudi za literarno teorijo in filozofijo. Magistrsko delo se na določeni ravni ukvarja z literarno teorijo in njenimi nezdružljivimi pristopi. Celo skozi analizo *Pijevega življenja* vidimo potrebo za združenjem. Zgolj en sam pristop ni bil dovolj za popolno analizo dela. Potrebne so bile skupne moči. Iz starega pristopa so izposojene določene stvari, ki so očitno delovale dovolj dolgo in so enostavno bile nadgrajene z novim pristopom. Ne stari ne nov pristop nista uporabljena v celoti. Kar je razumljivo – zakaj bi namreč tako naredili s starim pristopom, saj le-ta gotovo ni zadostoval, če obstaja novi. Vendar, zakaj bi vzeli samo del novega, po analogiji boljšega, in ne celote? Odgovor tiči v tem, da sta oba pristopa v eni točki tako sveža kot zastarela. Stari pristop je bil nekoč nov in nov pristop bo enkrat star in tako v nedogled. Da bi prekinili ta neskončen krog, v katerem je vsak novi pristop obsojen, da postane star v določeni točki in v katerem niti eden od nešteto novih pristopov ni nikoli rešil težave, ki naj bi jo rešil, je pomembno kombinirati stari in novi pristop. V primeru analiziranja *Pijevega življenja* je tako razmišljanje pripeljalo do boljše in bolj kompletne interpretacije.

Pijevo življenje je interpretirano s kombiniranjem dveh različnih pristopov in roman sam zagovarja kombinacijo religije in znanosti, ko gre za definiranje namena družbe. Če tako razmišljanje razširimo na filozofijo in vprašanje človeka, bi bilo razumno zagovarjati kombinacijo obeh filozofskih šol. Antični in kontinentalni filozofi bi morali delati skupaj, da bi rešili neskončno vprašanje človeka. Skupaj lahko filozofi razjasnijo vprašanje človeka veliko prej in lahko ponovno vzpostavijo mesto filozofije v družbi ob boku znanstvenikov.

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Izjava o avtorstvu

Izjavljam, da je magistrsko delo v celoti moje avtorsko delo ter da so uporabljeni viri in literatura navedeni v skladu s strokovnimi standardi in veljavno zakonodajo.

Ljubljana, 31. avgusta 2015

Stella Aslani